

**“ROLE OF MAGNETIC RESONANCE
VENOGRAPHY IN EVALUATION OF CEREBRAL
VEINS AND SINUSES OCCLUSION”**

By

Dr. NIHAR DOGGALLI

Dissertation submitted to the

**B.L.D.E. (DEEMED TO BE UNIVERSITY) VIJAYAPURA,
KARNATAKA**

In partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of

DOCTOR OF MEDICINE

In

RADIO-DIAGNOSIS

Under the guidance of

DR RAVI KUMAR DNB

ASSOCIATE PROFESSOR

DEPARTMENT OF RADIO-DIAGNOSIS

B.L.D.E.U'S SHRI B. M.PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE

HOSPITAL & RESEARCH CENTRE, VIJAYAPURA

KARNATAKA

2024

B.L.D.E. (DEEMED TO BE UNIVERSITY)

**SHRI B. M. PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE, HOSPITAL &
RESEARCH CENTRE, VIJAYAPURA**

DECLARATION BY THE CANDIDATE

I, **Dr. NIHAR DOGGALLI**, hereby declare that this dissertation entitled “**ROLE OF MAGNETIC RESONANCE VENOGRAPHY IN EVALUATION OF CEREBRAL VEINS AND SINUSES OCCLUSION**” is a bonafide and genuine research work carried out by me under the guidance of **Dr. RAVI KUMAR**, Associate Professor, Department of **RADIODIAGNOSIS**, B.L.D.E.U’s Shri B. M. Patil Medical College Hospital and Research Centre, Vijayapura.

Date:

Place: Vijayapura

Nihar.D

Dr. NIHAR DOGGALLI

Post Graduate Student,
Department of Radiodiagnosis,
B.L.D.E.U’s Shri B. M. Patil Medical
College, Hospital & Research Centre,
Vijayapura

B.L.D.E. (DEEMED TO BE UNIVERSITY)

**SHRI B. M. PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE, HOSPITAL &
RESEARCH CENTRE, VIJAYAPURA**

CERTIFICATE BY THE GUIDE

This to certify that the dissertation entitled “**ROLE OF MAGNETIC RESONANCE VENOGRAPHY IN EVALUATION OF CEREBRAL VEINS AND SINUSES OCCLUSION**” is a bonafide research work done by **Dr. NIHAR DOGGALLI**, under my overall supervision and guidance, in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the degree of M. D. in RADIODIAGNOSIS.

Date:

Place: Vijayapura

Dr. RAVI KUMAR DNB.

Associate Professor

Department of Radiodiagnosis,
B.L.D.E.U's Shri B. M. Patil Medical College,
Hospital & Research Centre, Vijayapura

B.L.D.E. (DEEMED TO BE UNIVERSITY)

**SHRI B. M. PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE, HOSPITAL &
RESEARCH CENTRE, VIJAYAPURA**

ENDORSEMENT BY THE HEAD OF DEPARTMENT

This to certify that the dissertation entitled “**ROLE OF MAGNETIC RESONANCE VENOGRAPHY IN EVALUATION OF CEREBRAL VEINS AND SINUSES OCCLUSION**” is a bonafide research work done by **Dr. NIHAR DOGGALLI** under the guidance of **Dr. RAVI KUMAR**, Associate Professor, Department of Radiodiagnosis at B.L.D.E.U’s Shri B. M. Patil Medical College Hospital and Research Centre, Vijayapura.

Date:

Place: Vijayapura

Dr. RAJASHEKHAR MUCHCHANDI M.D.

Head of Department

Department of Radiodiagnosis,

B.L.D.E.U’s Shri B. M. Patil Medical College,
Hospital & Research Centre, Vijayapura

B.L.D.E. (DEEMED TO BE UNIVERSITY)

**SHRI B. M. PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE, HOSPITAL &
RESEARCH CENTRE, VIJAYAPURA**

ENDORSEMENT BY THE PRINCIPAL

This to certify that the dissertation entitled “**ROLE OF MAGNETIC RESONANCE VENOGRAPHY IN EVALUATION OF CEREBRAL VEINS AND SINUSES OCCLUSION**” is a bonafide research work done by **Dr. NIHAR DOGGALLI** under the guidance of **Dr. RAVI KUMAR**, Associate Professor, Department of Radiodiagnosis at B.L.D.E.U’s Shri B. M. Patil Medical College Hospital and Research Centre, Vijayapura.

Date:

Place: Vijayapura

Dr. ARAVIND PATIL

Principal, B.L.D.E.U’s

Shri B. M. Patil Medical College,

Hospital & Research Centre, Vijayapura

B.L.D.E. (DEEMED TO BE UNIVERSITY)

**SHRI B. M. PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE, HOSPITAL &
RESEARCH CENTRE, VIJAYAPURA**

COPYRIGHT

DECLARATION BY THE CANDIDATE

I hereby declare that the B.L.D.E. UNIVERSITY, VIJAYPUR, Karnataka shall have the rights to preserve, use and disseminate this dissertation/thesis in print or electronic format for academic/research purposes.

Date:

Place: Vijayapura

Nihar D

Dr. NIHAR DOGGALLI

Post Graduate Student,

Department of Radiodiagnosis,

B.L.D.E.U's Shri B. M. Patil Medical

College, Hospital & Research Centre,

Vijayapura

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This piece of work has been accomplished with the grace of almighty God. I take this opportunity to extend my sincere gratitude and whole hearted thanks to all those who helped me complete this dissertation.

*I express my gratitude and sincere thanks to my guide, **Dr. RAVI KUMAR**_{DNB}, Associate Professor, Department of Radiology, B.L.D.E.U's Shri B. M. Patil Medical College, Vijayapura, for his constant support, professional insight, valuable suggestions, motivation and guidance to carry out and complete this dissertation. I am deeply grateful to him for providing me necessary facilities and excellent supervision to complete this work.*

*I offer my sincere thanks to Prof. (**Dr.**) **R.S.Mudhol**, Vice Chancellor; **Dr. Aravind Patil**, Principal and **Dr. Rajesh M.Honnutagi**, Medical Superintendent B.L.D.E.U's Shri B. M. Patil Medical College, Vijayapura for their support and inspiration.*

*My thanks to Professor and Head of the Department **Dr Rajshekhar Muchchandi** _{MD}; Professor **DR .Shivanand patil** ,Associate professors **Dr. Satish D. Patil** _{M.D}; **Dr. Siddaroodha Sajjan** _{DNB} and **Dr. Vishal S. Nimbale** _{DNB}; Assistant professors **DR Nagesh Wadgera** , **DR Pundalik Lamani** Senior Residents **DR MM Patil** _{DMRD} **Dr. Suresh Kanamadi** _{MD}, Department of Radio-diagnosis, B.L.D.E.U's Shri B. M. Patil Medical College, Vijayapura, for their valuable suggestions and encouragement which have definitely helped me improve my research work.*

My heartfelt thanks to my beloved parents, my sister and my grandparents for their constant support, trust and encouragement.

*I acknowledge my gratitude to My seniors **Dr. Shaurya**, **Dr. Shraddha**, **Dr. Ayesha** and **Dr. Saad**, my Postgraduate colleagues **Dr. Jayanth**, **Dr. Goutham**, and **Dr. Sumana** ,my juniors **Dr. Anudeep**, **Dr. Vaishnavi**, **Dr. Sumaya** ,**Dr. Prama**, **Dr. Siddharth**, **Dr. Deep***

Department of Radiology, B.L.D.E.U's Shri B. M. Patil Medical College, Vijayapura, for their support, advice and help in data collection.

I thank Statistician Mrs. Vijaya for her masterly guidance and statistical analysis. I sincerely acknowledge the support and kindness shown towards me by all the staff of Central Library, Shri B. M. Patil Medical College, Vijayapura, at all times.

Last but not the least, my sincere thanks to all the patients of this study for their cooperation without which this study would not have been possible.

Dr. Nihar Doggalli

Date:

Place: Vijayapura.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

ADC	APPARENT DIFFUSION CO EFFICIENT
CT	COMPUTED TOMOGRAPHY
CVO	CEREBRAL VENOUS OCCLUSION
CVT	CEREBRAL VENOUS THROMBOSIS
DWI	DIFFUSION WEIGHTED IMAGING
DSA	DIGITAL SUBTRACTION ANGIOGRAPHY
FOV	FIELD OF VIEW
GRE	GRADIENT RECALLED ECHO
ICOVT	ISOLATED CORTICAL VENOUS THROMBOSIS
MIP	MAXIMUM INTENSITY PROJECTION
MPR	MULTIPLANAR REFORMATED
MRI	MAGNETIC RESONANCE IMAGING
MRV	MAGNETIC RESONANCE VENOGRAPHY
PC	PHASE CONTRAST
RF	RADIOFREQUENCY
SAH	SUB ARACHNOID HAEMORRHAGE
SSS	SUPERIOR SAGITTAL SINUS
TE	TIME TO ECHO
TR	TIME TO REPEAT

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Sr. No.	Title	Page No
1	INTRODUCTION	11
2	OBJECTIVES	13
3	REVIEW OF LITERATURE	14
4	METHODOLOGY	63
5	RESULTS	65
6	DISCUSSIONS	83
7	CONCLUSION	91
8	SUMMARY	93
9	BIBLIOGRAPHY	94
10	ANNEXURES	
(i)	CONSENT FORM	107
(ii)	CASE PROFORMA	110
(iii)	MASTER CHART	122
11	IMAGE GALLERY	124
12	ETHICAL CLEARANCE CERTIFICATE	135
13	PLAGARISM	136

LIST OF TABLES

	Table	Page number
Table 1	IMAGING PROTOCOL	66
Table 2	SEX-WISE DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS WITH CVT	67
Table 3	AGE-SPECIFIC DISTRIBUTION OF CVT PATIENTS	68
Table 4	CAUSE-WISE DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS WITH CVT	69
Table 5	SYMPTOMS-WISE DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS WITH CVT	70
Table 6	DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS WITH CVT DEPENDING ON PARENCHYMAL CHANGES	72
Table 7	DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS WITH CVT DEPENDING ON PRESENCE OF COLLATERALS	73
Table 8	DISTRIBUTION OF CVT PATIENTS ACCORDING TO SAH PRESENCE	74
Table 9	DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS WITH CVT ACCORDING TO DIFFUSION WEIGHTED IMAGING	75
Table 10	DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS WITH CVT DEPENDING ON SINUSES INVOLVED	77
Table 11	DETECTION OF SUPERIOR SAGITTAL SINUS THROMBOSIS WITH MRV AND T1/T2 FLAIR WEIGHTED SEQUENCES.	79
Table 12	DETECTION OF LEFT TRANSVERSE SINUS THROMBOSIS WITH MRV AND T1/T2 FLAIR	80

	WEIGHTED SEQUENCES.	
Table 13	DETECTION OF RIGHT SIGMOID SINUS THROMBOSIS WITH MRV AND T1/T2 FLAIR WEIGHTED SEQUENCES.	81
Table 14	DETECTION OF RIGHT TRANSVERSE SINUS THROMBOSIS WITH MRV AND T1/T2 FLAIR WEIGHTED SEQUENCES.	82
Table 15	DETECTION OF LEFT SIGMOID SINUS THROMBOSIS WITH MRV AND T1/T2 FLAIR WEIGHTED SEQUENCES.	83
Table 16	DETECTION OF CORTICAL VENOUS THROMBOSIS WITH T2* AND T1/T2 FLAIR SEQUENCES	84
Table 17	DETECTION OF THROMBOSED DEEP VENOUS SEGMENTS WITH MRV, T2* AND T1 SEQUENCES	85

INTRODUCTION

Intraluminal blockage caused by cerebral venous thrombosis (CVT) or external compression is known as cerebral venous occlusion (CVO).

Although it is less prevalent than artery disease as a cause of cerebral infarction, its possible morbidity makes it a significant factor to take into account. ¹

A mysterious and frequently misdiagnosed cause of abrupt neurological decline is cerebral veno-occlusive disease. Because clinical symptoms and indicators are frequently non-specific, imaging is essential for this disorder's identification ².

The precise incidence of CVT is a matter of controversy due to the dearth of scientifically organized epidemiological research in the body of literature now in circulation. Research has indicated that the death rate ranges from 5 to 15%.

The fact that CVT affects people of all ages, its vast range of clinical manifestations, and its predisposing variables all work together to make the identification of the condition exceedingly tricky ⁴

In every neuroradiologic patient, the diagnostic checklist should include an evaluation for signs of CVT.⁵

The cerebral venous system has been seen using a variety of radiologic techniques. Our capacity to identify this problem has improved because to the use of conventional and digital subtraction cerebral angiography, CT, MRI, and, more recently, MR venography and CT venography⁶.

The gold standard for CSVT diagnosis is cerebral angiography. However, in certain cases, even targeted injections into the internal or common carotid arteries may not totally obstruct the dural sinuses. Angiography poses a 2% risk of major

Introduction

morbidity and mortality, is intrusive, can take a long time, and may result in local thrombosis at the site of catheter insertion⁷.

Conventional CT approaches underestimate the incidence and magnitude of venous infarcts as well as the degree of sinus involvement, missing the occurrence of CSVT in 16–40% of children and adults 7–8. Furthermore, CT can produce results that are falsely positive.

For the diagnosis of cerebral Sino venous thrombosis, CT venography is just as reliable as MR venography. The use of IV contrast material and considerable ionizing radiation exposure are two drawbacks of CT venography. Furthermore, CT cannot be utilized for repeated follow-up or as a screening method in patients who are pregnant⁶.

In the past ten years, Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) has demonstrated its efficacy as a substitute for this approach. When combined with MR venographic (MRV) techniques, MRI is quickly emerging as the preferred modality for the diagnosis and assessment of cerebral venous thromboses and dural sinus thromboses in locations where MRI facilities are accessible.⁹

The most popular technique for diagnosing cerebral venous thrombosis is TOF MR Venography.¹⁰

The gold standard for studying this condition is now the combination of MRI and MRV, which enables an accurate diagnosis of CVT.¹¹

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- **To assess the role of Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) and Magnetic Resonance Venography (MRV) as an imaging modality for early diagnosis of CVST.**
- **Correlation of MR Venography diagnosis with clinical features of CVT.**
- **To study patterns of venous thrombosis, in detecting changes in brain parenchyma and residual effects of CVST using MRI.**
- **To correlate the findings in MRV with FLAIR/ Diffusion weighted imaging sequences of brain.**
- **To correlate ADC values in detecting parenchymal abnormalities such as vasogenic / cytotoxic edema.**

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

OVERVIEW OF HISTORICAL ASPECTS-

In 1828, Abercrombie wrote the first report of thrombosis of the superior sagittal sinus (SSS) in adolescence. The clinical history of a 45-year-old man with disseminated cancer was documented by Ribes in 1925. The man passed away following a six-month period of headache, seizures, and delirium. After death, post mortem testing revealed thrombosis in the left lateral sinus, the parietal region, and a cortical vein.¹³ Subsequently, Kalabagh noted in his monograph on CVT that aseptic thrombosis is a common occurrence, particularly in young people, the puerperium, and the elderly.¹⁴

Since then, a large number of case reports and series—the majority derived from autopsy material—have been published. These contributed to the canonical description of a rare and severe condition characterized by focal deficits, headache, papilledema, seizures, progressive coma, and death. The sickness was also assumed to be pathologically associated with a hemorrhagic infarction, which contraindicates the use of anticoagulants.¹⁵

With the development of venography in 1951, the diagnosis of cerebral venous sinus thrombosis was improved. Prior to the development of CT, conventional CT was regarded as the preferred noninvasive method for diagnosing CVT.

Since MR has been used for around 20 years to diagnose CVT, Currently, when considering a CVT diagnosis clinically, MR with MRV is the preferred modality.

16, 17, 18, 19

ANATOMY OF INTRACRANIAL VENOUS SYSTEM:

Compared to architecture of the arteries, the intracranial venous system is a far more complicated, three-dimensional structure that is frequently asymmetric and changeable. Using a craniofugal strategy, we address the cerebral venous system from deep to cortical to dural. The supratentorial compartment is examined first in this section, and then the infratentorial compartment.

DEEP VENOUS SYSTEM:

According to Lasjaunias' classification scheme, the deep venous system can be classified into two distinct levels: (1) the internal cerebral vein, which includes the basal vein of Rosenthal, the great cerebral vein of Galen, and the internal cerebral vein; and (2) the transcerebral venous system. The deep venous system is responsible for the centripetal venous drainage of the deep cerebral white matter and basal ganglia. Due to the hemodynamic balance between these two levels, there is frequently some overlap and variance in their venous drainage.

Within the tela choroidea on the third ventricle's roof, close to the midline, are the two internal cerebral veins. Although structural variation in this location is widespread, the internal cerebral vein starts at the interventricular foramen of Monro, where it is produced by the confluence of the septal, anterior caudate, ventricular, choroidal, and terminal (thalamostriate) subependymal veins. The great cerebral vein (of Galen) is formed by the posterior union of the internal cerebral veins in the rostral region of the quadrigeminal cistern.²⁰

After circumnavigating the anteromedial portion of the lateral ventricle and draining the deep tissues of the frontal lobes, the septal vein travels posterior to the

foramen of Monro, where it joins the internal cerebral vein. Several caudate veins feed into the internal cerebral vein or the thalamostriate vein, respectively, from the caudate nucleus. The internal cerebral vein is typically fed by the thalamostriate vein, which is a significant tributary that drains the posterior frontal and anterior parietal lobes, caudate nucleus, and internal capsule. The superior and inferior choroidal veins drain the choroid plexus, and they either empty into the internal cerebral vein straight away or first to the thalamostriate vein.²⁰

Deep within the sylvian fissure, close to the medial region of the anterior temporal lobe, the Rosenthal basal vein receives numerous cortical (temporal) tributaries, cerebral peduncles, and veins emptying the insula. The basal vein joins the great cerebral vein (of Galen) or internal cerebral vein after running posteriorly near the base of the brain and bending around the cerebral peduncles.

Beneath the corpus callosum's splenium, the great cerebral vein (of Galen) is a short, unpaired midline structure that curves posteriorly. At the tentorial apex, it joins the inferior sagittal sinus to form the straight sinus.²⁰

The cerebral hemisphere's white matter is drained by a network of deep and superficial medullary veins known as the transcerebral veins. Because of their tiny size, transcerebral veins are usually not visible during angiography until specific conditions are met that change their normal hemodynamic state.²⁰

SUPERFICIAL CEREBRAL VEINS

Draining the cortex and a section of the subjacent white matter, the superficial cerebral veins run the length of the brain's surface. Despite having a very varied appearance, the superficial middle cerebral vein, superior anastomotic vein, and

inferior anastomotic vein are three prominent cortical veins that are frequently recognized individually. When one of the final two anastomotic veins is dominant, the other is typically hypoplastic or missing because of the reciprocal link between them.²⁰

Smaller veins draining the lateral surface of the hemisphere are received by the superficial middle cerebral vein, which travels anteriorly along the lateral (sylvian) fissure. This massive vein flows around the frontal lobe of the brain and empties either inferiorly into the pterygoid plexus or medially into the cavernous sinus. The superficial middle cerebral vein can empty in several directions thanks to anastomotic channels. These comprise the inferior anastomotic vein (of Labbe'), which opens into the transverse sinus, and the superior anastomotic vein (of Trolard), which opens into the superior sagittal sinus. Together with the Trolard vein, there are a variety of additional superiorly directed superficial cortical veins, often numbering between 10 and 12, that empty into the superior sagittal sinus.²⁰

DURAL VENOUS SINUSES

Blood finally travels from the venous sinuses, where the cerebral veins empty, into the internal jugular veins. The periosteal and meningeal layers of dura enclose the valveless dural venous sinuses.

SUPERIOR SAGITTAL SINUS:

It stretches from the foramen cecum to the torcular Herophili and is located at the connected edge of the falx cerebri. The superior sagittal sinus gathers the superficial cerebral veins that drain the cerebral convexities as it progresses posteriorly, increasing in caliber. Arachnoid granulations are seen extending into

the superior sagittal sinus along their route; these granulations are found within venous lacunae and can result in typical filling deficiencies on imaging exams.²⁰

INFERIOR SAGITTAL SINUS:

It drains the anterior portion of the corpus callosum, the medial parts of the cerebral hemispheres, and the inferior free edge of the falx cerebri. The great cerebral vein (of Galen) joins the inferior sagittal sinus, which extends posteriorly, to produce the straight sinus.

STRAIGHT SINUS:

Resides where the tentorium cerebelli and falx cerebri attach. It ends at the internal occipital protuberance, continues posteroinferiorly, and is often contiguous with the left transverse sinus. The union of the transverse, straight, and superior sagittal sinuses forms the torcular Herophili confluence of sinuses, albeit the confluence's appearance is frequently asymmetrical and very varied.²⁰

TRANSVERSE SINUSES:

It is located inside an occipital bone groove along the tentorium cerebelli's connected margin. Every transverse sinus travels anterolaterally before turning inferomedially to form the sigmoid sinus, which is located in the temporal bone's sigmoid sulcus, upon reaching the base of the petrous section. The cerebellum, the inferolateral temporal and occipital lobes, and, if it is present, the anastomotic cortical vein of Labbe supply the transverse sinus with multiple major veins. The

transverse sinuses continue anteroinferiorly as the sigmoid sinuses. The internal jugular veins emerge from these sinuses at the jugular foramen after draining into the jugular bulbs. Most transverse sinuses are lopsided, with majority of cases having a dominant right transverse sinus.

There is even a chance that the transverse sinus's medial and lateral halves are missing.²¹

Transverse sinuses were discovered to be right, left, and codominant in 59%, 25%, and 16% of the cases studied, respectively, in a study by Ayanzen et al²².

CAVERNOUS SINUSES:

Are a key intersection of intracranial and extracranial venous systems, located on either side of the sphenoid body. A cavernous sinus is a multi-compartmental extradural region that starts at the temporal bone's petrous section and ends at the superior orbital fissure. The abducens nerve and the cavernous section of the internal carotid artery are enclosed by this sinus, while the oculomotor, trochlear, and ophthalmic division of the trigeminal nerves are located between the dural leaves of the sinus's lateral wall.²⁰

THE SUPERIOR PETROSAL SINUS runs along the tentorium cerebelli's connection to the petrous portion of the temporal bone, connecting the posterior section of the cavernous sinus to the transverse sinus.²⁰

INFERIOR PETROSAL SINUS: Also arises from the cavernous sinus's posterior part, but it goes along the petro-occipital fissure postero laterally in a groove before typically ending by connecting to jugular bulb.²⁰

SPHENOPARIETAL SINUS: It empties into the cavernous sinus from the Sylvian vein, the superficial middle cerebral vein, and is often located along the lesser wing of the sphenoid.²⁰

THE SMALL VARIABLE OCCIPITAL SINUSES

Extends from foramen magnum to drain upward into the torcular Herophili, lying in the midline at the connection of the falx cerebelli.⁵¹ The occipital sinus, which is typically solitary but can occasionally have two, is correlated with the lateral sinus's size. In situations where the lateral sinus is primitive, it serves as the primary drainage canal²³.

INFRATENTORIAL VEINS

The posterior fossa's veins pool into three main drainage systems: the superior vein of Galen and its tributaries, the anterior petrosal sinuses, and the posterior dural sinuses that surround the tentorium cerebelli's leaves or in between them. Most of these deep and superficial venous systems are not often visible on MR venography, in contrast to the dural sinuses and supratentorial veins.²⁰

FIG 1 a

1b

Normal cerebral MRV. 3D TOF images obtained post IV Gadolinium in the coronal (a), sagittal (b) planes. There is visualization of Dural sinuses, superficial and deep cerebral veins. Superior sagittal sinus (blue arrow), straight sinus (yellow arrow), vein of Galen (purple arrow), internal cerebral vein (brown arrow), basal vein of Rosenthal (grey arrow), Torcular herophili (white arrow), lateral sinus (red arrow), sigmoid sinus (green arrow), internal jugular vein (orange arrow). The superficial cerebral veins (arrow head).¹⁶

EPIDEMIOLOGY

RISK FACTORS:

There are about a hundred causes of CVT documented in the scholarly literature. Up to 80% of patients have identifiable risk factors. However, in 20–25% of cases—despite thorough investigations—no reason is found.²⁴

According to Virchow, thrombosis can be caused by three factors: sluggish flow, coagulation problems, and damage to the vessel wall. Unlike arterial thrombosis, cerebral venous thrombosis is caused by damage to the artery wall in only approximately 10% of instances; in these situations, infection, infiltration, or trauma are the underlying causes of the condition. Coagulation problems are more significant (70%)²⁵.

The following are the main causes and risk factors of CVT:

Protein C, protein S, and antithrombin deficiency are examples of genetic prothrombotic disorders.

Pregnancy, puerperium, and nephrotic syndrome are acquired prothrombotic conditions.

Otitis media, mastoiditis, sinusitis, and meningitis are infections.

Sarcoidosis, Bechet syndrome, and systemic lupus erythematosus are examples of collagen-vascular disorders.

Hematologic disorders include sickle cell disease, anemia, polycythemia, and leukemia.

Drugs: oral contraceptives and tamoxifen

Other factors include: injuries, neurosurgery operations, cancer and dehydration¹.

PATHOLOGY

There are significant distinctions in the pathophysiology of venous and arterial thrombosis. According to some descriptions, CVST is a chronic process that disturbs the equilibrium between prothrombotic and thrombolytic processes, eventually causing the venous thrombus to progress. The good collateralizations of

the venous veins and the slow formation of the thrombus likely account for the symptoms' typically gradual start, which sometimes occurs over weeks or months. On the other hand, sudden onset has been reported. Given the high proportion of patients whose neurological disability is fully reversible, a sizable region of cerebral tissue that is only momentarily and reversibly disrupted must exist.²⁶

Secondary parenchymal alterations could result from cerebral bleeding, vasogenic edema, or cytotoxic edema. Higher venous pressure is most likely the main underlying cause. Subsequent parenchymal alterations may transpire if collateral routes of venous drainage are inadequate, particularly when cortical venous involvement is present. Cell death could occur if venous pressure keeps rising and subsequently lowers arterial perfusion pressure. Parenchymal alterations may partially or totally resolve if sufficient collateral routes grow or recanalization takes place prior to cell death or intracranial hemorrhage.¹⁰

Superior sagittal sinus thrombosis is suggested by bilateral parasagittal hemisphere abnormalities. Transverse sinus thrombosis²⁷ is characterized by ipsilateral temporo-occipital and cerebellar lobe abnormalities. Suspicion of deep cerebral vein thrombosis should be raised in cases of bilateral thalamic abnormalities. Thirty percent of individuals with deep cerebral venous thrombosis also have damage to other brain areas next to the thalami, including the mesencephalon and basal ganglia.²⁸

“The following vessels are involved in cerebral venous thrombosis in decreasing order, according to data from the largest cohort ever published (624 patients), which was gathered over a brief period of time: the superior sagittal sinus (62%), straight sinus (18%), left and right transverse sinuses (44.7% and 41.2%), cortical

veins (17.1%), deep venous system (10.9%), cavernous sinus (1.3%), and cerebellar veins (0.3%).”²⁹

Transcortical medullary veins may become sources of collateral blood outflow following dural sinus thrombosis. These arteries subsequently dilate, making them apparent on contrast-enhanced CT³⁰. The predominance of the dural collaterals is the cause of tentorial enlargement³². Occasionally, small subdural hematomas or effusions are observed.

It is rare for cerebral venous thrombosis to appear as a single SAH of the convexity.^{32, 33, 34}

INCIDENCE:

The true incidence of CVT is unknown in the absence of epidemiologic studies. In a series of 12,500 corpses, Ehlers and Courville found only 16 SSS thromboses, and in 20 years, Barnett and Hyland found only 39 noninfective CVTs. According to Kalbag and Woolf, from 1952 to 1961, the primary cause of death in England and Wales was only 21.7 individuals each year due to CVT. The true incidence may be ten times higher than previously believed based on autopsy data, according to a more recent publication of large clinical series, as the current mortality rate is roughly 10%.²⁶

According to Pillai et al., 10–20% of youth strokes in India are caused by CVT.³⁵

AGE:

While CVT can affect people of any age, ranging from newborns to the elderly, young people are the ones who experience it most frequently. The majority of patients—nearly 80%—are under 50.³⁶

Men with CVT had a consistent age distribution, according to Ameri and Bousser et al., however 61% of women with CVT were between the ages of 20 and 35. This could be connected to using oral contraceptives or getting pregnant ⁷.

With a mean age of 32.27 years, Pillai et al.'s research in the Indian context revealed that CVT is a significant cause of stroke in the young population. As such, it should be taken into consideration in all cases of young stroke and neurological disorders in the proper setting ³⁵.

SEX RATIO:

Women are primarily affected by dural sinus thrombosis (F: M = 3:1). Almost two thirds of women with CVT have at least one gender-specific risk factor, which includes oral contraceptives, pregnancy, puerperium, and hormone replacement treatment.

Women's mean age of presentation is over ten years lower than men's (34 vs. 42 years) due to these gender-specific risk factors. ³⁶

According to a research by Ameri and Bousser, the ratio of women to men is 1.29:1.7.

Ferro et al.³⁷ conducted a study which revealed that a modest preponderance in females is likely caused by factors such as OCPs, pregnancy, and puerperium. Studies on the female population during pregnancy and the puerperium have revealed that while CVT can happen at any time, the risk appears to be highest in the first two weeks of the puerperium ^{38, 39}.

CLINICAL FEATURES

“The signs and symptoms vary depending on which sinus is involved, and whether the thrombotic process is restricted to the dural sinus or spreads to the cortical veins plays a significant role in both”²³.

“In 70–90% of instances, the presenting symptom is a headache. In one-third to three-quarters of cases, focal impairments such hemiparesis and hemisensory disturbance, seizures, impairment of awareness, and papilloedema occur⁴¹.

Acute, subacute, or insidious onsets are possible; most patients arrive with symptoms that have developed over several days or weeks. Several common clinical constellations exist: A third group of between 30% and 50% of cases may present with seizures, frequently followed by a Todd's paresis. 18–38% of cases present with a syndrome resembling benign intracranial hypertension with headache, papilloedema, and visual disturbances; up to 75% of cases are characterized by a focal neurological deficit and headache”. Rare characteristic clinical presentations include cavernous sinus thrombosis (3%) with chemosis, proptosis, and severe ophthalmoplegia, and superior sagittal sinus thrombosis (4%) with bilateral or alternating deficits and/or seizures. Even less common is a fast-progressing disease with pyramidal symptoms, headache, nausea, and a worsening coma brought on by widespread involvement of the deep cerebral veins.

Thunderclap headache with neck stiffness mimicking SAH has been described.

The most common cause of a 6th nerve palsy is intracranial hypertension; however, thrombus extension to the jugular vein (IX–XI), petrosal sinus (V) and transverse sinus or sigmoid sinus (III– VIII) can also cause cranial nerve palsies.⁴¹

Cerebellar vein thrombosis produces more gradual-onset clinical symptoms

Review of literature

(headache, vertigo, vomiting, ataxia, and occasionally decreased awareness)
similar to those of arterial-territory infarcts in the cerebellum.^{40, 43}

RADIOLOGICAL INVESTIGATIONS

1) CONVENTIONAL ANGIOGRAPHY

“Carotid arteriography with delayed filming technique to visualize the venous system was the procedure of choice in the diagnosis of venous thrombosis prior to the advent of MRV. It is an invasive procedure and is therefore associated with well known associated risks.”^{44, 45, 46}

“Classical findings include Filling defects from thrombus within the venous sinuses, Occlusion of the draining sinuses, an angiographic empty delta sign when the sinus is perpendicular to the imaging plane and abnormal cortical veins (broken or corkscrew-like).”⁴⁴

“Secondary indirect findings are decreased focal venous circulation around a thrombosed venous sinus, prolonged contrast blush in the brain parenchyma, tortuous vessels in the capillary and venous phases and collateral flow in dilated anastomotic vessels.”

“With classical findings the diagnosis is certain; however, several pitfalls exist such as prolongation of venous circulation arising from other etiologies, congenitally hypoplastic or absent dural venous sinus and prominent arachnoid granulations simulating thrombus”.⁴⁴

“However, in patients with subarachnoid hemorrhage and cerebral venous thrombosis, DSA should be considered to rule out other causes of rebleeding, such as distal aneurysm and dural arteriovenous fistula, before anticoagulant therapy is administered”.^{32,33,34}

2) COMPUTED TOMOGRAPHY:

“CT scan with or without contrast injection is usually the first investigation undertaken. It is extremely useful to rule out the many conditions that can mimic CVT”.

“In can occasionally detect lesions that can themselves cause CVT, such as meningiomas, abscesses, sinusitis, or mastoiditis. It is also useful in showing brain or sinus changes suggestive of CVT”.⁴⁴

DIRECT SIGNS OF CVT

The delta sign: “On noncontrast CT scan, the classic finding is the delta sign, which is observed as a dense triangle (from hyperdense thrombus) within the superior sagittal sinus. However, this is not specific, since high attenuation in the healthy nonthrombosed sinus can be observed occasionally and is common in neonates because of an elevated hematocrit.”⁴⁴

This sign is reported in 20% of patients and takes approximately 1–2 weeks to disappear³⁰

The empty (reverse) delta sign: “appears after contrast injection and reflect the opacification of collateral vein in the SSS wall contrasting with the non-injection of clot inside the sinus. It is most frequent direct sign. However, it is absent when thrombosis does not affect the posterior third of SSS or when CT is performed in the first five days after onset of symptoms or more than two months later. 44 The empty delta sign is seen in 25%–75% of cases in the literature”^{30,31}

The cord sign: “Visible on plain CT represents thrombosed cortical veins. It can also be seen in internal cerebral vein and vein of Galen thrombosis”.⁴⁴

INDIRECT SIGNS OF CVT

Intense contrast enhancement of the falx and tentorium: “is present in 20% of cases. It indicates venous stasis or hyperemia of the duramater. It can be associated with dilated transcerebral medullary veins indicating a major venous stasis, usually in relation to an extensive SSS thrombosis”.

Parenchymal changes: “A common finding is the presence of diffuse low density suggestive of edema. However, this is a non-specific sign and is frequently difficult to differentiate from normal brain, particularly in the young.”⁴⁴

Venous infarction is the most specific indirect sign on unenhanced CT images. An infarction not conforming to a major arterial vascular territory, such as the presence of multiple isolated lesions, involvement of a subcortical region with sparing of the cortex, and extension over more than one arterial distribution, is highly suspicious for a venous cause. The infarction may be hemorrhagic or nonhemorrhagic”.⁵

“One should be aware that in 10–30% of cases of CVT, the findings on either unenhanced or contrast-enhanced CT are negative. Therefore, in highly suspicious cases, further evaluation with CT venography, or MRI with MR venography, is warranted”.⁵

CT VENOGRAPHY

“CT venography with bolus power injection of contrast material provides exquisite anatomic detail of the deep and superficial intracranial venous system and can directly demonstrate thrombus as filling defects”.

“CT venography has proved to be a reliable method to investigate the structure of the cerebral veins, with a reported sensitivity of 95% with multiplanar reformatted (MPR) images when compared with digital subtraction angiography (DSA) as the standard of reference”⁴⁷.

“Reported advantages of CT venography compared with MR imaging techniques are rapid image acquisition (reduction of motion-related artifacts), no contraindication to pacemaker and ferromagnetic devices, increased imaging resolution, and fewer equivocal imaging findings. No flow related artifacts have been reported with use of a contrast material bolus and acquisition in the venous phase”^{48,49,50}. “CT venography more commonly shows sinuses or smaller cerebral veins with low flow as compared with MR venography (2D phase contrast, 3D phase contrast, and 2D time of flight)”⁵⁰. “These two techniques probably provide comparable performance, and preference will be dictated by the experience and resources of the individual institutions”.⁵ “In a study by Ozsvath et al. the authors concluded that CT venography is superior to MR venography in identifying cerebral veins and dural sinuses and is at least equivalent in diagnosing dural sinus thrombosis”.⁵⁰

“Limitations of CT venography include exposure to ionizing radiation, adverse reactions to iodinated contrast medium, and limited visualization of skull base structures in 3D display”.²⁷

“In conclusion, CT venography is as accurate as MR venography in diagnosing CVT. CT venography can be used as a reliable alternative to MR venography in evaluating patients with clinically suspected CVT, especially in the acute setting”.⁶

FALSE-NEGATIVE CASES ON UNENHANCED CT

“Lack of increased density of a thrombosed dural sinus can be due to transition of a previously hyperdense dural sinus to one that is isodense with brain , volume averaging of a dural sinus with normal tissue and a small dural sinus, even when hyperdense, can be difficult to visualize against the high-density background of adjacent skull”.⁵¹

FALSE-NEGATIVE CASES ON CONTRAST-ENHANCED CT

“On occasion a so-called empty delta sign is not seen even though its depicted on catheter angiography due to the high density of thrombus that is not visible against the background of contrast enhancement of the walls of the dural or because the thrombus is partially recanalized.”⁵¹

FALSE-POSITIVE CASES ON UNENHANCED CT

“A high hematocrit (e.g. polycythemia vera) can cause a hyperdense sinus . This problem of a hyperdense appearance of the dural sinuses is also frequently encountered in infants and young children, in whom the relative density of the dural sinus compared with brain tissue is typically high for two reasons: first, a usually higher hematocrit value than in adults and, second, a typically lower brain density than in adults⁵¹. A Subdural hematoma may also mimic CVT”.⁵

FALSE-POSITIVE CASES ON CONTRAST-ENHANCED CT

“Normal variant structures located within a dural sinus, such as fenestrations and arachnoid Granulations ⁵¹ and variant Anatomy of the Sinus Confluence such as a high or asymmetric bifurcation may resemble an intrasinus thrombus”. ⁵²

FIG 2 a & b

Axial nonenhanced CT image (a) shows a —dense triangle sign (arrowhead) and a cord sign (arrow), findings suggestive of sinus and cortical vein thrombosis.

Three-dimensional integral image from CT venography (posterosuperior view) (b) shows filling defects in the superior sagittal sinus and Parieto-occipital veins, an appearance indicative of thrombosis.²⁷

FIG 3 a & b

Review of literature

Axial contrast-enhanced CT image (a) shows thrombosis of the left transverse and sigmoid sinuses (arrows).

Three dimensional integral image from CT venography (b) shows filling defects in the left transverse sinus and temporo-occipital veins, an appearance consistent with thrombosis.²⁷

a.

b.

FIG 4 a. b & c

Axial CT images from three patients with sinus thrombosis. (a) Typical irregularly shaped right frontal lobe hemorrhage (arrows) in a patient with superior sagittal sinus thrombosis. (b) Right temporal lobe hemorrhage with extensive edema (arrow) in a patient with right transverse sinus thrombosis. (c) Small subcortical hemorrhages (arrows) in the left frontal and parietal lobes in a patient with superior sagittal sinus thrombosis.¹⁰

3) ULTRASONOGRAPHY

“In general, Ultrasonography is not useful except in neonates where the diagnosis of venous sinus thrombosis may be made by color Doppler ultrasound. In young infants, the presence of an open fontanel enables the use of ultrasound to image the brain and Sino venous system. Cranial ultrasound is useful for defining centrally located venous infarcts or hemorrhages in infants with CVT. Though the technique is highly operator-dependent, it can be very useful and effective in skilled hands. Doppler ultrasound can define absent or reduced flow in the sinovenous channels in CVT, although this technique is most successful at defining complete occlusion of the superior sagittal sinus. The major limitation of Doppler ultrasound is in the evaluation of lateral venous sinuses when there is incomplete occlusion of residual flow may be mistaken for normal flow”.^{53, 54}

4) MRI AND MR VENOGRAM

T1-W images – “We need to use a short TR and a short TE to enhance the T1 differences between tissues. T1-weighted images usually have excellent contrast: fluids are very dark, water-based tissues are mid-grey and fat-based tissues are

very bright. They are often known as ‘anatomy scans’, as they show most clearly the boundaries between different tissues”.

T2-W images- T2 images require long TR and long TE, so they take longer to acquire than T1- weighted images. On these scans fluids have the highest intensity and water- and fat-based tissues are mid-grey. T2 images are often thought of as ‘pathology’scans because collections of abnormal fluid are bright against the darker normal tissue ⁵⁵

FLAIR.—In FLAIR sequences, an inversion recovery pulse is used to null the signal from cerebrospinal fluid ⁵⁶. When the net magnetization vector of cerebrospinal fluid passes its null point, little or no longitudinal magnetization is present in the fluid. The transverse magnetization of cerebrospinal fluid is insignificant, and therefore no signal is generated. Elimination of the signal from cerebrospinal fluid is useful for detecting lesions that otherwise are not easily distinguishable or for delineating hyperintense lesions that border fluid-containing spaces such as sulci or ventricles in the brain ⁵⁷

GRE Sequences - In a GRE sequence, an RF pulse is applied that partly flips the net magnetization vector into the transverse plane ⁵⁸. Gradients, as opposed to RF pulses, are used to dephase and rephase transverse magnetization. Because gradients do not refocus field inhomogeneities, GRE sequences with long TEs are T2* weighted (because of magnetic susceptibility) rather than T2 weighted like SE sequences. GRE sequences are sensitive to magnetic field inhomogeneity secondary to magnetic susceptibility differences between tissues This feature of GRE sequences is exploited for the detection of hemorrhage, as the iron in

haemoglobin becomes magnetized locally and thus dephases the spinning nuclei.

57

Diffusion-weighted Imaging- Diffusion weighting enables one to distinguish between rapid diffusion of protons (unrestricted diffusion) and slow diffusion of protons (restricted diffusion) ⁵⁹. For diffusion-weighted imaging, either an echo-planar or a fast GRE sequence is used and two equal gradient pulses are applied (one on each side of the 180° RF pulse in echo-planar sequences). If no net movement of spinning nuclei occurs between the applications of the gradient pulses, the first gradient dephases the spins and the second rephases them; therefore, high signal intensity is seen. If there is net movement, the protons are not affected by both gradients (they may undergo dephasing but not rephasing, or vice versa); therefore, the signal intensity is decreased⁵⁷

MAGNETIC RESONANCE VENOGRAPHY (MRV)

Several methods are available to image veins with MRI, including contrast-enhanced and non–contrast-enhanced pulse sequences.

NON–CONTRAST-ENHANCED (NCE) TECHNIQUES:

MRV can be divided into bright-blood and dark-blood techniques on the basis of without contrast use. Bright-blood method is more common and reliable. Bright-blood NCE MRV pulse sequences are time-of-flight (TOF) sequences, phase contrast (PC) sequences and steady state free precession (SSFP) sequences.

TIME-OF-FLIGHT MRA: TOF MR Angiography is based on the principle of flow-related enhancement and highlights differences in magnetization between

nuclei in flowing blood and those in stationary tissue. TOF MR angiographic methods have included both 2D and 3D techniques, although the latter is considered much inferior when visualizing the intracranial venous system, primarily because of signal loss from in-plane saturation.

The typical characteristics of 2 D TOF MRA include a conventional gradient echo (GRE) sequence, short repetition time (TR), intermediate or high flip angle, and short echo time (TE). The orientation of the acquisition plane is selected to be perpendicular to the main direction of flow and is typically coronal when imaging the intracranial venous system. Spatial presaturation pulses are commonly applied either above or below each slice to reduce signal from overlapping arteries or veins and thereby select for flow in one direction or the other. In these methods, stationary tissue reaches a steady “saturated” state of magnetization as it is exposed to repeated radiofrequency (RF) excitation pulses throughout the imaging process and appears dark or intermediate shades of gray. By contrast, fresh blood flowing into an image section perpendicular to the plane of the acquisition retains significantly higher magnetization strength, as it has not been subjected to these RF pulses (i.e., it is unsaturated”) and therefore appears as high contrast bright blood” signal. Maximum intensity projection (MIP) images can be created by combining the data from multiple 2D TOF sections.²⁰

2D-TOF imaging is exquisitely sensitive to slow flow, it nevertheless has a minimum threshold below which sufficient signal from flowing blood cannot be obtained. If flowing spins within the selected 2D slice slab are not replenished by TR, which is usually on the order of 45 to 50 milliseconds, these spins become

subject to repeated pulses and become saturated, as do the surrounding stationary tissues, resulting in signal loss from the selected slice. This signal loss, if severe, can result in the production of artefactual flow gaps within a vessel. To overcome this problem, it is desirable to set the slice thickness as small as possible, typically on the order of 1.0 to 1.5 mm.

To overcome artefactual signal loss resulting from in-plane vascular flow, it is desirable to orient the acquisition plane perpendicular to the long axis of the vessel being imaged. Because the bulk of the intracranial venous flow is in an anteroposterior direction, toward the torcular Herophili, slice acquisitions in the coronal plane satisfy the requirement of perpendicular orientation during acquisition for a majority of the intracranial dural sinuses. Although this improves signal from vessels that are oriented predominantly in the sagittal plane (superior sagittal sinus, straight sinus, and so on), signal loss can become a potential problem in the region of the torcular Herophili and posterior aspect of the superior sagittal and transverse sinuses, as these segments gradually become coplanar with the imaging plane. Conversely, 2D-TOF imaging in the sagittal plane alone, which would be expected to improve the signal and enhance visualization of these posterior regions, would be suboptimal for showing the superior sagittal sinus, straight sinus, inferior sagittal sinus, portions of the sigmoid sinuses, and so forth.^{60,61,62.}

The major advantage of 2D TOF MR Angiography is that it is sensitive to slow flow and has relatively short acquisition times. Its main disadvantages include insensitivity to in-plane flow and high signal from substances with short T1 values

(e.g., fat, methemoglobin, Gd) that can mimic flow because of incomplete saturation and “shine through” on the MIP reconstruction. Magnetization transfer saturation can be used to decrease the signal intensity of background tissue without affecting blood, thereby further increasing contrast between them and possibly helping to overcome this limitation.²⁰

In 3D TOF an RF pulse is applied to a large slab (typically 50mm thick) and a second loop of phase encoding is performed to partition the slab into many thin partitions (typically 0.7mm thick) ⁶³

PHASE CONTRAST MRA: Phase-contrast MRA is based on the principle of using velocity-induced phase shifts to depict flowing blood. In contrast with stationary tissue, spins moving through a magnetic field will experience a phase shift that is proportional to the velocity of flow, amplitude of the bipolar gradients, and time interval between the gradient lobes.

The typical characteristics of PC angiography include a conventional GRE sequence, bipolar (flow encoding) gradients along one or more axis, and a velocity encoding variable (VENC) that adjusts the bipolar gradient strength to produce a phase shift of 180°. PC images are reconstructed from two or more data sets that are usually acquired simultaneously in an interleaved fashion. One data set acts as a reference GRE phase without flow encoding, whereas the others are acquired when the bipolar gradients are applied along the x, y, and z axes. In this way, the 3D PC angiographic data set combines flow-sensitive transverse, coronal, and sagittal images to visualize the intracranial venous system.

The major advantages of PC MRA are the greater suppression of background (stationary) tissues, and the ability to quantify flow and determine flow direction. Although 3D PC MRA is comparable to 2D TOF techniques in visualization of intracranial venous structures, its disadvantages include relatively long acquisition times and the need to predict the optimal VENC which is generally not known in advance.²⁰

2D PC angiography is unsuitable for visualisation of intracranial venous structures because substantial intravascular signal loss occurred because of intravoxel dephasing that occurred because of large voxels used in this technique⁶⁴

GADOLINIUM-ENHANCED THREE-DIMENSIONAL MRA: Gadolinium-enhanced 3D MRA is gaining wide clinical acceptance in a variety of vascular applications including the intracranial venous system . It is not a TOF technique and does not depend on the inflow of unsaturated spins. Rather, the paramagnetic effect of Gd shortens the intravascular T1 relaxation time, thus increasing the signal intensity of blood with no saturation effects. In this way, the contrast between blood and stationary tissue becomes relatively flow-independent. In a manner analogous to conventional catheter angiography, Gd-enhanced 3D MRA thereby produces a “lumenogram” with contrast enhancement of the intravascular space.

The typical characteristics of Gd-enhanced 3D MRA include a conventional GRE sequence, keeping TR and TE as short as possible, and using an intermediate flip angle to keep background tissue sufficiently saturated and provide an image of the

passing contrast bolus. For optimal image quality, the injection profile must be timed so that the contrast bolus is maximally present within the vessels of interest during acquisition of the low k-space frequencies. An acquisition that is too early or too late may miss the peak passage of contrast bolus and produce inadequate vascular visualization. To this end, MR-compatible injectors and automated bolus tracking software to trigger scan acquisition may be employed.

The major advantages of Gd-enhanced 3D MRA are the much superior visualization of intracranial venous morphology, greater suppression of unwanted background signal, and avoidance of saturation effects that are often problematic with the TOF technique.

Perceived disadvantages of Gd-enhancing 3D MRA might include issues of cost of the contrast agent, accompanying cost of the power injector and supplies, patient discomfort of obtaining antecubital intravenous (IV) access, and training of the MR technologists.²⁰

ATECO 3D Gd-ENHANCED MR VENOGRAPHY: A new novel technique called auto triggered elliptic centric ordered (ATECO) 3D Gd-enhanced MR venography has been developed. The ATECO MR venographic examination consists of four integral stages: (1) initiation of an axial 2D bolus detection sequence located at the level of the cavernous carotid arteries; (2) power injection of an IV contrast material; (3) automated detection of the arrival of intra-arterial Gd-based contrast material at the cavernous carotid level, resulting in automatic termination of the detection sequence, and triggering of (4) a fast 3D GRE MR angiographic sequence with elliptical centric ordered phase encoding.

Coordination of the IV injection and 3D centrically encoded scan is performed using a software based “triggering tool”. Interactive slice positioning at the level of the skull base permits the MR technologist to position a region of interest (ROI) over the carotid and basilar arteries and determine a signal intensity-triggering threshold. Saturation bands active during the detection sequence extinguish unwanted flow-related arterial enhancement. The subsequent IV bolus injection of Gd-based contrast material results in a rapid rise in signal intensity within the ROIs that exceeds the set threshold. The 3D MR angiographic sequence is automatically triggered after an empirically determined eight-second delay to ensure sufficient contrast material perfusion has advanced well into the intracranial venous system prior to initiation of the centric filling of k-space.⁶⁵

IMAGE RECONSTRUCTION

Post processing techniques are useful because they provide a comprehensive display of complex vascular anatomy. A 3D acquisition facilitates post processing techniques. Frequently used algorithms are multiplanar reconstruction (MPR), maximum intensity projection (MIP), and volume rendering.⁶⁶

MULTIPLANAR RECONSTRUCTION

For MPRs, extraction of 2D projection is made from 3D volume information. The MPR algorithm permits cross-sectional interrogation of the 3D volume of data in any desired plane. Hence, MPR images sometimes can demonstrate complex 3D anatomy of tortuous vessels better than the source images.⁶⁶

MAXIMUM INTENSITY PROJECTION (MIP)

MIP is a post processing technique that produces 3D images. With MIP, a projection ray is passed through the volume of data so that the data is projected on a 2D plane. Instead of summing the signal intensity along the rays, a projective image is calculated by penetrating the data volume with a set of parallel projection rays and selecting along each of these rays only the data point that represents the intensity maximum. This process is repeated at different angles. Subsequently, the images are combined to produce 3D perception of vascular structures.⁶⁶

DIRECT VOLUME RENDERING

Volume rendering is a technique that provides high quality 3D images. Volume rendering is a twostep process consisting of classification and rendering, classification is a process of determining tissue types and assigning brightness levels/colors to each voxel. During classification, a partial transparency (0 – 100%) is assigned to tissue or signal-intensity classes. Rendering is a second stage of this technique; it involves image projection to form a simulated 3D image. External and internal structures can be evaluated with direct volume rendering.⁶⁶

To summarize, the techniques to study the intracranial venous system with MRI currently include unenhanced TOF MR Venography, Phase-contrast MR venography and contrast- enhanced MR venography. Phase-contrast MR venography is less often used, because of its dependence on operator defined

velocity encoding parameters. TOF MR Venography is the method most commonly used for the diagnosis of cerebral venous thrombosis¹⁰

However Studies have shown MR contrast based techniques to be better than non contrast techniques and equivalent to conventional digital subtraction angiographic (DSA) images in the visualisation of cerebral venous anatomy¹⁶

VISUALISATION OF THROMBUS ON MR:

For the detection of venous thrombi Unenhanced MR imaging is more sensitive than unenhanced CT. Primary finding of sinus thrombosis on MR images is absence of a flow void and altered signal intensity.¹⁰

The signal intensity of venous thrombi on T1- and T2-weighted MR images varies according to the interval between the onset of thrombus formation and the time of imaging^{15,17,67}. The change in signal intensity is related to the paramagnetic effects of the products of hemoglobin breakdown in the thrombus^{17,67}.

In the acute stage of thrombus formation (0–5 days), the signal is predominantly isointense on T1-weighted images and hypointense on T2-weighted images because of deoxyhemoglobin in red blood cells trapped in the thrombus. A venous thrombus in the acute stage may have a signal intensity that mimics a normal flow state and such a finding may lead to diagnostic error⁶⁸. Very hypointense signal on T2- weighted images may be mistaken for flow void. In 10%–30% of cases of sinus thrombosis, the thrombus at initial presentation or imaging examination is in the acute stage of formation^{68,69,70}. Contrast-enhanced MR venography or CT venography is necessary to achieve a definitive diagnosis at this stage.

In the subacute stage of thrombus (6–15 days), the signal is predominantly hyperintense on both T1-weighted images and T2-weighted images because of methemoglobin in the thrombus^{17,71}. Subacute-stage thrombus has been found in 55% of patients at clinical presentation with cerebral venous thrombosis^{69,70}. This stage of formation is the easiest stage at which to detect a thrombus on MR images, as the signal intensity of the sinus is most different from that in normal flow states. Increased signal intensity on both T1 and T2-weighted images is almost always abnormal.

Chronic thrombosis with incomplete recanalization of the sinus may present a diagnostic challenge at MR imaging. As many as 15% of patients in whom sinus thrombosis is diagnosed at MR imaging may have a chronic (15 days -old) thrombus^{69,70}. Compared with the MR signal in normal brain parenchyma, the signal in a chronic thrombus is typically isointense or hyperintense on T2-weighted images and isointense on T1-weighted images; however, significant variability in thrombus signal intensity exists^{15,69,71}. On images acquired after gadolinium administration, marked contrast enhancement may be observed that resembles the enhancement typically seen in a normal sinus. Sinus enhancement is presumably secondary to an organized thrombus with intrinsic vascularization as well as due to slow flow in dural and intrathrombus collateral channels. Contrast enhancement of the sinus on MR images does not definitively indicate patency, and venography usually is necessary for a definitive diagnosis.

As gradient-recalled echo (GRE) sequences are increasingly used in MR imaging protocols to detect the presence of blood breakdown products, their usefulness in depicting intraluminal thrombi in cerebral venous thrombosis has been appreciated⁷³. In stages of thrombus evolution in which paramagnetic products such as deoxyhemoglobin and methemoglobin are present, the sensitivity of GRE sequences to magnetic susceptibility produces blooming artifacts in the thrombosed venous segments on GRE images.

GRE imaging sequences may be an important diagnostic aid in acute-stage thrombosis, when the signal intensities on T1- and T2- weighted images may be more subtle⁴⁹.

There has been recent interest in evaluating the appearance of intraluminal venous thrombi on diffusion-weighted images. Signal hyperintensity in thrombosed sinuses on diffusion weighted images, with corresponding diminishment in the mean apparent diffusion coefficient (ADC) values, has been described in 41% of patients with sinus thrombosis. The duration of clinical symptoms was longer and complete recanalization was less frequent in patients with restricted diffusion in the thrombus⁶⁹.

The loss of the normal flow void on spin echo T2 images is a sensitive parameter. The T2 signal abnormality which replaces the normal signal void from the sinus is a more reliable sign of thrombosis as very slow flowing blood may occasionally give rise to give high signal on spin echo T1 weighted images even in the absence of any thrombus .

Thrombus on MRV is seen either as loss of high flow signal from the sinus, in cases of complete occlusion of the sinus or frayed and patchy flow signal in the presence of nonocclusive thrombus.

The demonstration of thrombus in cortical veins is very difficult due to the high degree of anatomic variations.^{16,18,22}

RECANALIZATION:

An irregular appearance of the sinus, with multiple intrasinus channels and dural collateral vessels, may be seen on MR venographic images and is characteristic of incomplete recanalization⁷¹. Complete recanalization may occur more often in thrombosis of the superior sagittal sinus and straight sinus than in thrombosis of the transverse and sigmoid sinuses after anticoagulation therapy⁷⁴.

Numerous venous collateral pathways may form after sinus thrombosis. Collateral vessels may form in the dura that surrounds the occluded sinus, arising from cortical veins that drain to nonthrombosed sinuses or from intermediate veins (ie, diploic, emissary, meningeal). The intermediate veins may form a dominant collateral system in the presence of extensive thrombosis³⁰.

PARENCHYMAL ABNORMALITIES:

Parenchymal lesions are better depicted and more commonly identified at MR imaging than at CT^{71,75}

Focal brain abnormalities have been identified in as many as 57% of patients with cerebral venous thrombosis. Focal edema (without visible hemorrhage) is visible

on CT images in approximately 8% of cases and on MR images in 25% of cases^{74,76, 77}.

Parenchymal swelling without abnormalities in attenuation or signal intensity on images may occur in as many as 42% of patients with cerebral venous thrombosis⁶⁷. Sulcal effacement, diminished cistern visibility, and a reduction in ventricular size may occur. Patients with brain swelling and without parenchymal signal intensity changes tend to have intrasinus pressures in the intermediate range (20–25 mm Hg); however, intrasinus pressures also may be markedly elevated⁷⁴

The conventional MR imaging findings of cerebral venous sinus thrombosis (CVT) are mass effect in most patients; hyperintense parenchymal abnormalities on a T2-weighted image that involve gray matter, white matter, or both in approximately 50–60% of patients and intraparenchymal hematoma in approximately 35–40%^{75,78}. Although some T2 hyperintense parenchymal abnormalities resolve, others persist and indicate permanent tissue injury. Lesion distribution does not differentiate between these two lesion types.⁷⁹

Parenchymal changes may be secondary to cytotoxic edema, vasogenic edema, or intracranial hemorrhage. Vasogenic and cytotoxic edema patterns may coexist.¹⁰

Hemorrhage may occur with both types of edema, and various patterns may coexist in the same region^{76,77}. In view of the variable nature of the parenchymal abnormalities that may occur in cerebral venous thrombosis, the use of the term venous infarct in reference to these lesions should be discouraged because that term implies irreversibility.

In contrast with arterial ischemic states, many parenchymal abnormalities secondary to venous occlusion are reversible. Although parenchymal changes may occur in areas of the brain that are directly drained by the occluded venous sinus, in some patients the parenchymal changes may not closely correlate with the location of venous occlusion^{74,80}.

Unlike conventional MR images, diffusion weighted (DW) MR images can differentiate between vasogenic and cytotoxic edema. Cytotoxic edema is characterized by markedly decreased diffusion⁸¹. Vasogenic edema, with increased interstitial water, demonstrates increased diffusion. In a study by Mullins et al⁸², they found that DW imaging, in combination with the clinical history (i.e., seizure), may be useful in differentiating parenchymal lesions that resolve from those that progress to permanent injury in the setting of acute CVT. In their retrospective cohort, lesions with elevated diffusion resolved, lesions with decreased diffusion resolved when the patient had seizures, and lesions with decreased diffusion in the absence of clinical seizure demonstrated abnormality on follow-up images.

The ADC values were similar between the lesions with low ADC values that resolved and the lesions with low ADC values that persisted. The T2 hyperintense parenchymal abnormalities may represent vasogenic edema, cytotoxic edema, or both.

Ten lesions characterized by elevated diffusion that showed essentially no abnormality on follow-up images were identified. These lesions likely represented vasogenic edema that is produced in CVT owing to increased pressure in the

postcapillary venules and opening of tight junctions. Lesions characterized by decreased diffusion that showed no abnormality on follow-up images were identified in three patients with seizure activity, possibly due to cytotoxic edema. The decreased ADC values in these patients may have resulted from the seizure activity. Animal and human studies have demonstrated decreased ADC values in cortical and white matter lesions in subjects with status epilepticus. The pathophysiology for decreased ADCs in epilepsy is not completely clear. Thus, while cytotoxic edema associated with acute arterial stroke is usually irreversible, cytotoxic edema associated with CVT may be reversible if the blood drains through collateral pathways. Five lesions characterized by decreased diffusion that showed abnormality on follow-up images were identified. These lesions likely represented persistent cytotoxic edema followed by tissue infarction. In these cases, there was likely severely decreased blood flow without enough collateral blood drainage to maintain adequate perfusion. This information may be important in prospectively determining severity of irreversible injury and inpatient treatment.⁸²

Hemorrhage.—Parenchymal hemorrhage can be seen in one-third of cases of cerebral venous thrombosis^{70,76,77,78,80}. Flame-shaped irregular zones of lobar hemorrhage in the parasagittal frontal and parietal lobes are typical findings in patients with superior sagittal sinus thrombosis and should prompt additional imaging evaluations (eg, with MR venography or CT venography). Hemorrhage in the temporal or occipital lobes is more typical of transverse sinus occlusion. Hemorrhage in cerebral venous thrombosis is typically cortical with subcortical extension. Smaller zones of isolated subcortical hemorrhage also may be seen⁸³

and may be accompanied by minimal edema. The mechanism of hemorrhage in cerebral venous thrombosis is multifactorial. Hemorrhage may be precipitated by continued arterial perfusion in areas of cell death, as can be seen at reperfusion in arterial ischemia

Elevation of venous pressure beyond the limit of the venous wall also is likely operative.

CONTRAST ENHANCEMENT.—

Parenchymal enhancement in 1%–29% of cases of cerebral venous thrombosis has been reported^{30, 73}. The enhancement is typically gyral in location and may extend into the white matter. Parenchymal enhancement, which indicates disruption of the blood-brain barrier, may be seen in areas of cytotoxic or vasogenic edema and in the presence of either irreversible or reversible brain abnormalities. Increased tentorial enhancement (likely related to dural venous collaterals), adjacent leptomeningeal enhancement, and prominent prominent cortical venous enhancement (secondary to venous congestion) also may be visible after the administration of contrast material.

PERFUSION CHANGES.

In a study performed in patients with normal ADC values, the most common finding was prolongation of the mean transit time with normal relative cerebral blood volume in areas of the brain that were drained by the thrombosed sinus⁸⁴. Alterations in mean transit time were seen in areas of the brain with and without parenchymal signal intensity alterations or hemorrhage. In patients who underwent

follow-up MR perfusion imaging after treatment and sinus recanalization, the perfusion abnormalities had resolved by the time of follow-up. measurements ⁸⁵

MR SPECTROSCOPIC FINDINGS.

Little information exists regarding MR spectroscopic findings in cerebral venous thrombosis. In one patient with deep venous occlusion and extensive thalamic edema, proton MR spectroscopic findings included a very mild lactate peak with preserved *N*-acetyl aspartate levels ⁸⁶. Arterial infarction generally produces a more pronounced diminishment in neuronal metabolites and a pronounced elevation of lactate levels. Very early arterial infarction may have a similar appearance, with an elevated lactate level and variably preserved *N* acetyl aspartate levels ⁸⁷.

ISOLATED CORTICAL VENOUS THROMBOSIS

Isolated cortical venous thrombosis is a relatively rare entity; fewer than 20 cases have been reported in the imaging literature disease ⁸⁸

Typical parenchymal findings are areas of focal cortical edema or hemorrhage, which may be nonspecific. The finding of an adjacent thrombosed venous structure, which may be the most specific sign of this disorder, has been mentioned in most recent descriptions of this entity ^{89,90}. On CT images, this finding has been referred to as the “cord sign”; on MR images, it has been called the “hyperintense vein sign”⁸⁹. When looking at GRE pictures, blooming artifacts inside thrombosed veins can be a very helpful supplementary finding.

According to a research by M. Boukobza et al ⁹¹. T2*GE is extremely valuable for the early diagnosis of ICoVT, an uncommon CVT presentation. When ICoVT is

diagnosed and treated, the cortical venous MSE seen on T2*GE images might last for several months or even years, in contrast to the temporary signal-intensity alterations on standard MR imaging.

FALSE-NEGATIVE CASES ON MRI

False-negative MRI cases are caused by thrombosed dural sinuses simulating normal signal intensity (normal brain tissue or normal blood flow). Acute thrombus may be isointense to the brain on T1-weighted imaging, making it less noticeable. Approximately 50% of cases on T1-weighted MRI showed an isointense signal of thrombus relative to cerebral tissue, according to one series⁹².

The existence of hypointense thrombus on T2-weighted imaging that simulates a flow void is another confounding factor; according to one study, this finding was present in almost 10% of the instances with DST⁶⁸. In a different series, only 27% of patients on the first MR scan had a hyperintense signal abnormality within a thrombosed dural sinus on T2-weighted images⁹³. In the enhancing venous sinus, thrombus is anticipated to cause a filling deficiency upon the administration of gadolinium-containing contrast agents. However, because of the capillary channels in the thrombus, contrast-enhanced T1-weighted images of DST in chronic stages can also occasionally show homogeneous contrast enhancement of the thrombosed dural sinus (often with accompanying pulsation artifact), making it challenging to distinguish from a patent dural sinus.

FALSE-POSITIVE CASES ON MRI

On spin-echo MR sequences, false-positive cases occur when a dural sinus's signal intensity mimics a thrombus'. The principal reasons for the lack of the predicted flow void within a dural sinus ²⁷ include sluggish flow, in-plane flow, and entry-slice abnormalities. According to reports, children under the age of two are most likely to have this challenge ⁷⁸.

FALSE-POSITIVE CASES ON MR VENOGRAPHY:

It is linked to a false positive rate of 9% ^{94, 95}.

Variations in the size of the dural sinuses, hypoplastic or aplastic dural sinuses, and anatomic abnormalities that result in filling deficiencies, such as septations and arachnoid granulations, can all be anatomic reasons of false-positive findings. ⁵¹.

Septations, also known as fibrotic bands, are more commonly seen on contrast-enhanced magnetic resonance imaging (MR venography) as opposed to tof MR venography. They manifest as linear filling deficiencies in the sinuses. Because arachnoid granulations show up on MRI as filling deficiencies, they can mimic thrombus.

Flow-related artifacts as well as those unique to different MR venography methods might result in signal loss that mimics thrombus.

Artifactual intravascular signal voids may arise in TOF venography when flow parallel to the plane of acquisition (in-plane flow) causes signal loss due to signal

saturation from inflowing protons. The distal sigmoid sinus and the internal jugular veins are examples of vertically oriented structures where signal loss from in-plane flow is most noticeable because acquisitions in TOF venography are often carried out in the coronal plane.

On TOF MR Venography generated using source images in the axial plane, an inferior saturation band utilized to saturate artery signal can result in false-positive findings mimicking nonexistent flow in the anterior and center regions of the superior sagittal sinus. This observation is explained by the fact that blood flow in the front region of the superior sagittal sinus follows arterial blood flow, or more specifically, flows cephalad. As a result, the anterior part of the superior sagittal sinus as well as the arteries are saturated by the inferior saturation pulse used in TOF MR Venography. This augmentation associated with flow loss might go far into the sinus's central region.⁵¹

FALSE-NEGATIVE CASES ON MR VENOGRAPHY:

It has a 24% false negative rate correlation^(94, 95). On unenhanced T1-weighted images, the signal generated by hyperintense thrombus can mimic flow within the dural sinus on TOF MR Angiography, leading to a false-negative result.

FIG 5

T1 w sagittal image. The superior sagittal sinus is heavily thrombosed. The thrombus is giving variable signal with the older thrombus in the anterior part giving a hypertintense signal (Black arrows, and fresh thrombus in the posterior part giving isointense T1 signal (Black arrows).

FIG 6

T2 w axial image. There is an absent signal void in the anterior superior sagittal sinus (Black arrows) representing thrombus, with normal flow void (White arrows) in the posterior part of the superior sagittal sinus.

i

ii

iii

FIG 7 i, ii & iii

Subacute thrombus of superior sagittal sinus. Axial T1- W (i) and Axial T2-W (ii) An abnormally elevated signal intensity is visible in the superior sagittal sinus on MR images. (white arrow). (iii) The contrast-enhanced MR venography's sagittal source picture displays filling deficiencies (white arrows) caused by a thrombi.¹⁰

FIG 8

Oblique MIP image from TOF MR Venography in a patient having left transverse sinus and superior sagittal sinus thrombosis; observe the atypical morphology of the superior sagittal sinus (arrows), indicating partial sinus recanalization.

A

B

FIG 9 A & B

Thrombosis of the internal cerebral veins, the vein of Galen, and the straight sinus. (A) The axial intermediate-weighted picture displays widespread anomalies in the signal that extend into the nuclei of the caudate and inside the thalami (arrows). (B) Two-dimensional Sagittal phase-contrast Magnetic Resonance The venogram shows a section of the deep venous system that is signal-free (arrows), which is in line with blockage.¹⁰

a.

b.

c.

FIG 10 a, b & c

The DWI (a) and the T2-W image (b), which were acquired at the time of presentation, demonstrate a region of elevated signal intensity that is compatible with diffusion restriction along the right parietal lobe's cortex (arrow in a) and the accompanying aberrant T2 signal (arrowheads in b). In the superior sagittal sinus, there is also a visible high-signal-intensity thrombus (arrow in b). (c) A seven-month-old T2-weighted picture demonstrates resolution of the thrombus (arrow) and negligible atrophy in the zone of prior diffusion restriction (arrowhead).¹⁰

FIG 11 A, B & C

Initial MR imaging on day seven, (A and B). The right precentral sulcus exhibits linear hypointensity on T2*GE images as a result of MSE at the location of the thrombosed veins (small arrow), and hypointense regions that correlate to cortical hemorrhages (long arrows). C, Only enlarged gyri (arrow) are visible on the T1-weighted picture.⁹¹

In conclusion, when the diagnosis of CVT is deemed clinically appropriate, magnetic resonance imaging (MR) in conjunction with magnetic resonance venography is the most sensitive diagnostic tool for that purpose 16, 17, 18, 19, 96,

When screening individuals with a low suspicion of CVT and nonspecific clinical presentation, unenhanced CT is still the method of choice. CVT can be diagnosed

more precisely with contrast-enhanced CT. CT venography is currently becoming a rival method. It has been demonstrated to be on par with MR venography and, in certain cases, to yield more accurate diagnostic data.

COMPLICATIONS

Although rare, a pulmonary embolism resulting from a dural sinus thrombosis has a dismal prognosis.

Venous sinus thrombosis may cause hypopituitarism.

Several authors have linked dural arterio-venous fistulas to DVST, though it can occasionally be challenging to determine whether thrombosis was the primary or secondary event.

After dural sinus thrombosis, focal seizures with or without secondary generalization may continue, necessitating ongoing anti-epileptic medication.⁹⁷

PROGNOSIS

The percentage of patients that fully recover functionally ranges from 57% to 86%. The mortality rate in recent series^{42,98} ranges from 5.5% to 18%. A lower prognosis is linked to multiple elements, notwithstanding the lack of a definite linkage between the severity of the disease and its result. The most significant ones are: early onset and advanced age; quick onset with coma and focused impairments; and thrombosis that mostly affects the deep vein system. The underlying illness has a negative impact on the prognosis, especially sepsis, cancer, and paroxysmal nocturnal hemoglobinuria. Twelve percent of patients had another

CVST episode, and fourteen percent experience another type of venous thrombosis.

TREATMENT

Thrombolytic therapy or anticoagulation is a specific treatment for CVT. The goal of anticoagulant therapy is to stop the original thrombus from spreading further and to enable the fibrinolytic system to dissolve the thrombus that has already formed. In contrast to an arterial ischemic stroke, venous blockage treatment may, even if it takes longer, reduce circulatory congestion and have a positive therapeutic impact⁹⁹.

Due to heparin's proven safety and the positive trend of clinical outcomes, heparin therapy is still the primary choice for CVT patients. According to a study's authors, an accompanying cerebral hematoma did not preclude the use of dose-adjusted intravenous (IV) heparin (unfractionated heparin, bolus dose of 3000 IU and continuous infusion of 25,000–65,000 IU/day) as an effective anticoagulation treatment.¹⁰¹

INTERVENTION - ENDOVASCULAR TREATMENT

Since 1988, numerous investigations have demonstrated the feasibility of directly infusing thrombolytic drugs by a percutaneous or retrograde transvenous method into the thrombosed dural sinus^{102,103,104}. The systemic hemorrhagic effect brought on by high-dose IV anticoagulation therapy may be avoided by administering thrombolytic therapy locally.

Within 29 hours of the rtPA treatment, 75% of the patients (completely in 50% and partially in 25%) had flow restoration, according to Frey et al¹⁰⁵. They showed that

the degree of flow restoration was directly correlated with clinical recovery.

Clinical deterioration is a possibility, nevertheless, particularly in those who have experienced cerebral hemorrhage.

There is currently no scientifically validated endovascular therapy regimen that includes inclusion or exclusion criteria, thrombolytic agent dosage, treatment duration, concurrent heparin use, and endpoint of the interventional procedures. In a research by Benamer et al., patients who demonstrated clinical worsening after receiving heparin therapy for 24 hours had endovascular treatment. Using a microcatheter, a rapid-pulsed direct-infusion approach was employed to administer 30 to 50 mg of rtPA over the course of 15 to 20 minutes. Not the total lack of thrombus within the dural sinus, but antegrade flow within the sinus was the angiographic target ; concurrent IV heparin was employed. According to the authors' observations, maintaining anticoagulation while reestablishing antegrade flow is adequate to provide clinical improvement.¹⁰⁶

A number of dural sinus revascularization methods, including mechanical disruption with guide wires, rheolytic thrombectomy catheters, balloon thrombectomy with fibrinolysis, transluminal balloon angioplasty, with or without stenting, and surgical thrombectomy, have been documented in addition to local thrombolytic treatment. In the case of severe cerebral venous hypertension, the function of endovascular closure of the dural sinuses with angioplasty and stent implantation is anecdotal, and long-term outcomes are unknown¹⁰⁷.

METHODOLOGY

SOURCE OF DATA

- Patients referred to the Radiology department, SHRI B.M.PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE, VIJAYAPURA.
- Those who fulfil the inclusion criteria.

METHODS OF COLLECTION OF DATA

Sample Size: 54 cases

Study design: Hospital based prospective study.

Period of Study: September 2022 to June 2024.

INCLUSION CRITERIA

- Patients of young and middle age of both sexes presenting with clinically suspected CVT who undergo MRV and MRI Brain sequences (FLAIR and DWI).

EXCLUSION CRITERIA

- All individuals with cochlear implants, pacemakers, artificial heart valves, or metallic implants in their bodies.
- Patients with past history of claustrophobia.
- Known patients of previous CVT on follow up.

Used imaging protocol

A 1.5 T GE SIGNA MRI machine was used to evaluate each subject. Axial T1 SE, Sagittal T1 FLAIR, Axial and Coronal T2 FSE, Axial FLAIR, Axial T2*, and 2D TOF were the sequences employed. After completing the two-dimensional (2D TOF) process in the sagittal plane, the source pictures were rebuilt into three-dimensional (3D MIP) maximum intensity projection images. The following sequence parameters applied.

TABLE 1: IMAGING PROTOCOL

	TE (ms)	TR (ms)	FOV (cm)	SLICE THICKNESS(mm)	MATRIX	NEX
AXIAL T1	9.5	700	261 x 261	5	320X206	0.5
AXIAL T2	102.9	4913	260 x 260	5	256X192	1
AXIAL FLAIR	92.9	8262	261 x 261	5	320X224	1
CORONAL T2	106.8	5914	230 x 230	5	320X224	1
AXIAL T2*	92.9	620	261 x 261	5	256X192	0.75
DWI	99.7	5131	260 x 260	5	120X140	4
2D TOF	5.6	12.3	250 x 250	5	320X192	0.62

RESULTS

A total of 54 patients were suspected clinically for cerebral venous thrombosis in a hospital based prospective study who underwent MR Venography were included in this study.

TABLE 2: SEX WISE DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS WITH CVT

Gender	No. of patients	percentage
Female	19	34.5
Male	36	65.5
Total	55	100.0

GRAPH 2: SEX WISE DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS WITH CVT

It was discovered that 66% of the patients in the current study were male, and 34% were female.

TABLE 3: AGE-SPECIFIC DISTRIBUTION OF CVT PATIENTS

Age(in years)	No. of patients	Percentage (%)
< 20	3	5.5
20 - 29	18	32.7
30 - 39	14	25.5
40 - 49	8	14.5
50 - 59	5	9.1
60 - 69	3	5.5
70+	4	7.3

GRAPH 3: AGE-SPECIFIC DISTRIBUTION OF CVT PATIENTS

Results

In the present study the commonest age group was found to be between 20-29yrs of age with 32.7 % of patients falling in this age group. This was followed by 30- 39yrs of age with 25.5 % of patients falling in this age group.

TABLE 4: DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS DEPENDING ON THE CAUSE OF CVT

CAUSE	No. of patients	percentage
ALCOHOL	13	23.6
DEHYDRATION	5	9.1
DEMYELINATING DISORDER	1	1.8
DIARRHEA	1	1.8
HYPERTENSION	2	3.6
MASTOIDITIS	1	1.8
ORAL CONT PILS	2	3.6
POSTPARTUM	8	14.5
SEPSIS	5	9.1
TRAUMA	4	7.3
UNKNOWN	13	23.6
Total	55	100.0

GRAPH 4: DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS DEPENDING ON THE CAUSE OF CVT

In present study the cause for CVT could not be found in 23.6% of cases. Alcohol was the most common cause of CVT (23.6%) among the cases when the reason was identified. It was followed by postpartum (14.5%), dehydration and sepsis (9.1%).

TABLE 5: DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS WITH CVT DEPENDING ON SYMPTOMS

SYMPTOMS	No. of patients	percentage
HEADACHE	30	54.54
NEUROLOGICAL DEFECIT	7	12.72
SEIZURES	18	32.72
LOSS OF CONSCIOUSNESS	5	9.09
ALTERED SENSORIUM	15	27.27
VOMITING	2	3.63
FEVER	1	1.81
GIDDINESS	9	16.36
BLURRING OF VISION	3	5.45

GRAPH 5: DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS WITH CVT DEPENDING ON SYMPTOMS

The most prevalent symptom in the current study was headache (54.56%), which was followed by seizures (32.72% of cases) and altered sensorium (27.27% of cases).

TABLE 6: DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS WITH CVT DEPENDING ON PARENCHYMAL CHANGES

PARENCHYMAL CHANGES	No. of patients	percentage
HI	28	50.9
NON-HI	5	9.1
NORMAL	21	38.1

GRAPH 6: DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS WITH CVT DEPENDING ON PARENCHYMAL CHANGES

The most common focal brain abnormality was a hemorrhagic infarction found in 51 % cases followed by nonhemorrhagic infarction in 10 % of cases.

TABLE 7: DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS WITH CVT DEPENDING ON PRESENCE OF COLLATERALS

COLLATERALS	No. of patients	percentage
YES	8	14.5
NO	47	85.5
Total	55	100.0

GRAPH 7: DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS WITH CVT DEPENDING ON PRESENCE OF COLLATERALS

In the current study, 14.5% of the subjects with CVT had collateral vessels.

TABLE 8: DISTRIBUTION OF CVT PATIENTS ACCORDING TO SAH PRESENCE

SAH	No. of patients	percentage
YES	5	9.1
NO	50	90.9
Total	55	100.0

GRAPH 8: DISTRIBUTION OF CVT PATIENTS ACCORDING TO SAH PRESENCE

9.1% of the CVT cases in the current study had subarachnoid haemorrhage.

TABLE 9: DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS WITH CVT ACCORDING TO DIFFUSION WEIGHTED IMAGING

EDEMA	No. of patients	percentage
CO EXIST	11	20.0
CYT ED	2	3.6
NO	35	63.6
VAS ED	7	12.7
Total	55	100.0

GRAPH 9: DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS WITH CVT ACCORDING TO DIFFUSION WEIGHTED IMAGING

The focal abnormalities in the current investigation were classified as co-existing cytotoxic and vasogenic edema in 55% of instances, vasogenic edema in 35% of cases, and cytotoxic edema in 10% of cases using diffusion weighted imaging.

TABLE 10: DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS WITH CVT DEPENDING ON SINUSES INVOLVED

SINUSES INVOLVED	No. of patients	percentage
SUPERIOR SAGITTAL	34	61.8
RIGHT TRANSVERSE	26	47.2
RIGHT SIGMOID	6	10.9
LEFT TRANSVERSE	17	30.9
LEFT SIGMOID	15	27.27
STRAIGHT SINUS	5	9.09
VEIN OF GALEN	1	1.81
INTERNAL CEREBRAL VEIN	1	1.81
CORTICAL VEINS	9	16.36

GRAPH 10: DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS WITH CVT DEPENDING ON SINUSES INVOLVED

The Superior Sagittal Sinus (61.8%) was the most often impacted sinus in the current study. It was followed by the right transverse sinus (47.2%), left transverse sinus (30.9%), left sigmoid sinus (27.27%), and cortical veins (16.36%).

TABLE & GRAPH 11: DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS WITH CVT INVOLVING SUPERIOR SAGITTAL SINUS DEPENDING ON MRV AND T1/T2 FLAIR WEIGHTED SEQUENCES DETECTION

	YES	NO	Chi –square(χ^2)	P -value
DETECTED BY T1w /FLAIR	34(61.8)	21(38.2)	0.000	P=1.00
DETECTED BY TOF	34(61.8)	21(38.2)		
Statistically insignificant.				

A non-significant difference in the number of patients with CVT between the MRV diagnosis and the T1 and T2 FLAIR diagnostic is revealed by the chi-square value of 0.000 and the probability value of 1.00.

TABLE & GRAPH 12: DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS WITH CVT INVOLVING LEFT TRANSVERSE SINUS DEPENDING ON MRV AND T1/T2 FLAIR WEIGHTED SEQUENCES DETECTION

	YES	NO	Chi –square(χ^2)	P -value
DETECTED BY T1 w /FLAIR	13(23.6)	42(76.3)	0.7331	P=0.3918
DETECTED BY TOF	17(30.9)	38(69)		
Statistically insignificant.				

A non-significant difference in the number of patients with CVT between the MRV diagnosis and the T1 and T2 FLAIR diagnostic is revealed by the chi-square value of 0.7331 and the probability value of 0.3918.

TABLE & GRAPH 13: DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS WITH CVT INVOLVING RIGHT SIGMOID SINUS DEPENDING ON MRV AND T1/T2 FLAIR WEIGHTED SEQUENCES DETECTION

	YES	NO	Chi –square(χ^2)	P- value
DETECTED BY T1 w /FLAIR	6(10.9)	49(89.1)	0.000	P=1.00
DETECTED BY TOF	6(10.9)	49(89.1)		

Statistically insignificant.

A non-significant difference in the number of patients with CVT between the MRV diagnosis and the T1 and T2 FLAIR diagnostic is revealed by the chi-square value of 0.000 and the probability value of 1.00.

TABLE & GRAPH 14: DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS WITH CVT INVOLVING RIGHT TRANSVERSE SINUS DEPENDING ON MRV AND T1/T2 FLAIR WEIGHTED SEQUENCES DETECTION

	YES	NO	Chi -square(X^2)	P -value
DETECTED BY T1 w /FLAIR	26(47.3)	29(52.7)	0.000	P=1.00
DETECTED BY TOF	26(47.3)	29(52.7)		
Statistically insignificant.				

A non-significant difference in the number of patients with CVT between the MRV diagnosis and the T1 and T2 FLAIR diagnostic is revealed by the chi-square value of 0.000 and the probability value of 1.00.

TABLE & GRAPH 15: DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS WITH CVT INVOLVING LEFT SIGMOID SINUS DEPENDING ON MRV AND T1/T2 FLAIR WEIGHTED SEQUENCES DETECTION

	YES	NO	Chi -square(X^2)	P -value
DETECTED BY T1w /FLAIR	20(36.4)	35(63.6)	0.000	P=1.00
DETECTED BY TOF	20(36.4)	35(63.6)		
Statistically insignificant.				

A non-significant difference in the number of patients with CVT between the MRV diagnosis and the T1 and T2 FLAIR diagnostic is revealed by the chi-square value of 0.000 and the probability value of 1.00.

TABLE & GRAPH 16: T2* AND T1/T2 FLAIR SEQUENCES FOR THE DETECTION OF CORTICAL VENOUS THROMBOSIS

	YES	NO	Chi -square(X^2)	P- value
DETECTED BY T1W /FLAIR	3(5.4)	52(94.5)	3.367	P=0.0565
DETECTED BY T*	9(16.3)	46(83.6)		
Statistically significant				

A significant difference in the number of patients with CVT between the T2* diagnosis and the T1/T2 FLAIR diagnostic is revealed by the chi-square value of 3.367 and the probability value of 0.0565.

TABLE & GRAPH 17: DETECTION OF THROMBOSED DEEP VENOUS SEGMENTS WITH MRV, T2* AND T1 SEQUENCES

	YES	NO	Chi –square(χ^2)	P value
DETECTED BY T1	2(3.6)	53(96.3)	9.131	P =0.0104
DETECTED BY T*	12(21.8)	43(78.1)		
DETECTED BY TOF	12(21.8)	43(78.1)		
Statistically significant				

The T2* / MRV diagnostic and the T1 diagnosis of the degree of thrombosis in the deep vein system differ significantly, as indicated by the Chi-Square value of 9.131 and the probability value of 0.0104. A significant difference between the diagnostic of MRV and the T1 and T2 diagnosis regarding the degree of thrombosis in the deep vein system.

DISCUSSION

Acute neurological decline can have a mysterious, frequently misdiagnosed cause: cerebral veno-occlusive illness.²

The diagnosis of CVT is very difficult due to a multitude of reasons, including a broad spectrum of clinical manifestations, several risk factors, and the fact that it impacts individuals of various ages.⁴

Imaging is vital to the diagnosis due to non-specific clinical signs and symptoms. The gold standard for studying this condition is now the combination of MRI and MRV, which enables an accurate diagnosis of CVT. The most effective noninvasive technique for assessing the cerebral venous system is MR venography.¹¹

It's thought that women experience CVT more frequently than men. Ameri and Bousser discovered that the female to male ratio in a set of 110 cases was 1.29:1.7. With 66% of the patients in this study being male, there appears to be a little male preponderance.

While CVT can affect anyone at any age, young people are the ones who experience it most frequently.³⁶

Among the Indian context, Pillai et al. discovered that CVT is a significant contributor to stroke among the younger generation, with mean age of 38.69 yrs and the most common age group being 20–29 years.³⁵

The mean age at presentation is almost ten years lower in women than in men (34 vs. 42 years) due to gender-specific risk factors.³⁶

According to the current study, the most common age group for patients was determined to be between the ages of 20 and 29 (32.7%). The age group of 30-39 years old came next, with 25.5% of patients falling into this category.

With a mean age of 42.5 years for male patients and 29 years for female patients, the patients' average age was determined to be 38.69 years.

In the present study alcohol (23.6%) and unknown (23.6%) was the commonest cause for CVT. It was followed by postpartum (14.5%), dehydration (9.1%) and sepsis (9.1%).

These findings corroborated those of Ameri and Bousser, who, after conducting thorough studies, concluded that there was no cause in 20–25 percent of instances.⁷

According to Nagaraj et al.¹⁰⁸ “puerperium was the most frequent predisposing factor. They discovered that 200 out of 230 cases (86%) of CVT seen over an eight-year period were puerperal in character.”

According to Bousser et al.¹⁰⁹, cerebral venous occlusion caused by thrombosis was seen in all 110 individuals in his study.

According to a study by Eman Abd-El Latif et al.¹, intraluminal thrombus accounted for 86.7% of cases of cerebral venous blockage.

Meningioma produced occlusion by external compression, which was observed in 13.3% of cases.

In the current investigation, intraluminal thrombus (CVT) accounted for 96.6% of the cases, with one instance resulting from external compression produced by a meningioma.

This contrasts with the findings of Jeffrey et al.¹¹⁰, who found that the primary cause of cerebral sinus occlusion caused by solid tumors was compression or invasion of the sinuses by dural or calvarial metastases.

The most common symptoms and indicators in a Dutch European study were paresis (unilateral or bilateral) in 30% of cases, focal seizures with or without secondary generalization in 34% of cases, and headaches (38%).¹¹¹

According to a research by Poon et al., headaches accounted for 75% of all symptoms, with seizures coming in second at 37% and motor/sensory deficits at 34%.⁵

This was in line with the results of the current study, which showed that headaches (66.6%) were the most common symptom, followed by seizures (33.3%) and neurological deficits (26.6%).

About half of the cases had focal alterations. The placement of the affected sinus may not coincide with the location of the parenchymal alterations.⁸⁰

According to Simonds et al.¹¹², “localized edema was present in 25% of the cases, non-hemorrhagic infarction in 40% of the cases, and hemorrhagic infarction in 26.7% of the cases”. According to Nagaraj et al.¹⁰⁸, 41.9% of patients had hemorrhagic infarction and 51.6% did not.

Hemorrhagic infarcts were the most common parenchymal lesions in a research by Khandelwal et al⁶ occurring in 60% of cases; nonhemorrhagic infarcts were observed in 13 % of patients.

In the current study, hemorrhagic infarctions accounted for 51% of all focal brain abnormalities, with non-hemorrhagic infarctions accounting for 10% of instances. Parenchymal alterations could be a result of cerebral bleeding, vasogenic edema, or cytotoxic edema. Patterns of cytotoxic and vascular edema may coexist.¹⁰ Both kinds of edema can cause bleeding, and different patterns can coexist in the same area^{76,77}. It is not advisable to refer to these lesions as "venous infarcts" due to the

diverse nature of the parenchymal abnormalities that can arise in cerebral venous thrombosis, as this term implies irreversibility. Diffusion weighted (DW) MR images, in contrast to conventional MR imaging, are capable of distinguishing between cytotoxic and vasogenic edema.

DW imaging was used to assess, 13 CVT patients in a research by Mullins et al.⁸² “Three types of lesions were found: low diffusion lesions that persisted, consistent with cytotoxic edema in patients without seizure activity; low diffusion lesions that resolved in patients with seizure activity. The elevated diffusion lesions were consistent with vasogenic edema”.

Vasogenic edema and cytotoxic edema were the two categories assigned to the focal abnormalities in the current investigation using diffusion weighted imaging. Fifty-five percent of the cases had both vasogenic and cytotoxic edema present, thirty-five percent had just vasogenic edema, and ten percent had only cytotoxic edema. Nevertheless, the cases were not monitored to see if the cytotoxic edema-related diffusion restriction remained.

“The following vessels are involved in cerebral venous thrombosis in decreasing order, according to data from the largest cohort ever published (624 patients), which was gathered over a brief period of time: the superior sagittal sinus (62%), straight sinuses (18%), left and right transverse sinuses (44.7% and 41.2%), cortical veins (17.1%), deep venous system (10.9%), cavernous sinus (1.3%), and cerebellar veins (0.3%).”²⁹ This was in line with the results of the current study, which showed that the Superior Sagittal Sinus (41.8%) was the most frequently

affected sinus, followed by the right transverse sinus (47.2%), left transverse sinus (30.9%), right sigmoid sinus (10.9% cases), and the straight sinus (9% cases). Two percent of instances involved the the internal cerebral veins, the basal vein of Rosenthal, vein of Galen and the cerebellar veins.

In 16.36% of instances, the superficial cortical veins were affected. Nevertheless, there were no instances of the superficial cortical veins being involved alone. Of the instances, collateral vessels were observed in 14.5 percent.

Seldom are reports of subarachnoid hemorrhage linked to cerebral venous thrombosis (CVT) found in the literature. Unknown is the precise cause of SAH linked to CVT. SAH may result from a subsequent rupture into subarachnoid spaces caused by a venous hemorrhagic infarct. Fragile, thin-walled cortical veins may burst in dural sinus thrombosis with subsequent venous hypertension, causing SAH into the subarachnoid space³².

Nonetheless, 5 individuals (or 9% of the cases) in the current study had subarachnoid hemorrhage. Concomitant parenchymal hemorrhagic infarctions were present in every patient.

The gold standard for studying this condition is now the combination of MRI and MRV, which enables an accurate diagnosis of CVT.¹¹

According to a study by Vogl et al.⁹, MR angiography is the preferred method for diagnosing and monitoring dural sinus thrombosis and is a reliable stand-alone assessment for this illness.

Flowing blood usually results in a signal void with spin-echo sequences; however, stagnant blood on thrombus has been found to produce a higher signal intensity. Nevertheless, this phenomenon is not totally dependable since thrombus can occasionally be mimicked by increased intraluminal flow signal that is caused by a number of flow-related aberrations.

Moment of takeoff Short repetition periods and movable flip angles in magnetic resonance imaging (MR angiography) enable the visualization of blood flow as regions of increased signal intensity set against a black background of reduced signal from immobile tissues.

The age of the thrombus seems to have some bearing on the outcomes of spin-echo MR imaging for CVT identification. However, signal intensities varied, making it difficult to distinguish between clear-cut halt of flow and low or normal flow, especially in the event of moderately severe thrombus.

In 80% of cases, an aberrant signal replaced the usual flow void on T1/T2 weighted images, according to a research by Khandelwal et al.⁶

In two instances, there was evidence of thrombus on CT and MR venography, but normal flow void and no parenchymal alterations were observed on routine MR sequences. This result highlights the significance of MR venography in all suspected cases of CVT, including in cases when standard MR results seem normal.

13 patients (23.6%) in the current study's 54 cerebral venous thrombosis patients with MRV confirmation had loss of flow voids identified on traditional T1 and T2

FLAIR weighted imaging. MRV verified CVT of the left transverse sinus in four patients (7.3%) despite the fact that conventional MRI did not clearly show a lack of flow void.

It is commonly known that slow flow, in plane flow, and entrance slice phenomena cause a lot of false positives on SE sequences. This, together with the differences we found in our research between MRV and conventional sequences for the diagnosis of thrombosed venous systems, however not statistically significant, supports the significance of using MRV in addition to conventional MRI for the diagnosis of CVT.

According to Leach et al.¹¹³, “susceptibility effects from CVT are most common in patients with hypointense thrombus on T2WI within 7 days of the onset of symptoms and can be identified with GRE imaging. Thirty-six of the sixty-nine thrombosed venous segments that were assessed showed obvious signs of embolism”.

There could be important susceptibility artifacts from the base of the skull. Without sinus involvement, or isolated CVT (ICoVT), is a relatively uncommon condition that has only been documented in small series or solitary case reports. For various reasons, ICoVT is particularly challenging to diagnose using merely T1-weighted, T2-weighted, and MRV imaging. The quantity, size, and position of cortical veins vary greatly, and it might be challenging to distinguish obscured tiny veins at the cortical level using these MR images.

According to a study by M. Boukobza⁹¹ et al., T2*GE is extremely valuable for the early detection of ICoVT. When ICoVT is diagnosed and treated, the cortical

venous MSE seen on T2*GE images might last for several months or even years, in contrast to the brief signal-intensity changes on standard MR imaging.

It was discovered that 9 patients (16.3%) in this study had cortical vein thrombosis. Nevertheless, no instance of solitary cerebral vein thrombosis was found. Only 3 (5.4%) of the 9 patients had cerebral vein thrombosis found on T1/T2 weighted pictures, but all 9 cases were found on T2 * images due to blooming artifact. Nonetheless, there was no statistically significant difference found in the identification of superficial cortical veins between the T2* and T1/T2 weighted sequences.

Two of the patients in the current study also had deep vein thrombosis. MRV and T2* imaging identified thrombosis in each of the 12 deep venous segments that were implicated in the two patients. Nevertheless, thrombosis was seen in a single Galen vein in one of the patients using T1/T2 FLAIR imaging. There was a statistically significant difference in the detection of thrombosed deep vein segments between the T1/T2 FLAIR weighted sequences and the T2*/MRV sequences.

The results given above demonstrate how crucial T2* sequences are for the identification of CVT.

Nevertheless, T2 * images were not utilized to identify thrombosis in the dural venous sinuses due to high susceptibility artifacts from the surrounding calvaria.

CONCLUSION

54 patients with cerebral venous thrombosis identified by MRV were included in our investigation.

In our study, the majority of patients were male. The age group that was discovered to be most common was 20–29 years old, with a mean age of 38.69 years. Perhaps as a result of risk variables unique to gender, women presented ten years earlier than men.

In 23.6% of the cases, alcohol and unknown were the most frequent causes of CVT.

Headache was shown to be the most frequent symptom, followed by seizures.

It was discovered that the most often affected sinus was the SSS.

About three-fourths of the cases had focal parenchymal alterations, with the frontal lobe being most frequently affected.

The most frequent focal parenchymal abnormality identified was hemorrhagic infarct. The non-hemorrhagic infarct came next.

The localized parenchymal alterations were identified as either cytotoxic or vasogenic edema using DWI, with the former being more prevalent. It is not advisable to refer to vasogenic edema as a venous infarct because it is reversible.

The ability to distinguish between vasogenic and cytotoxic edema with DWI is very valuable in determining the patient's prognosis.

In five of our patients, subarachnoid hemorrhage was found. These cases demonstrate how a CVT may be revealed by SAH and how it should be taken into account during the diagnostic process of SAH, particularly in cases when the basal cisterns are unaffected.

Conclusion

In every patient examined for our investigation, MRV revealed thrombosis. There was a minor difference found in the detection of cerebral venous thrombosis between MRV and traditional MRI sequences, with MRV performing better.

The T2* sequence was very helpful in identifying CVT, particularly in the deep venous system and the superficial cortical veins, as well as the hemorrhagic component of the parenchymal alterations. However, in our investigation, its application in detecting dural sinus thrombosis was hindered by considerable susceptibility artifacts from nearby calvaria.

SUMMARY

In summary, MR angiography is the preferred method for diagnosing and monitoring dural sinus thrombosis. The most complete, noninvasive, safe, diagnostic modality for vascular anatomy delineation, diagnosis of cerebral venous thrombosis (CVT) and its extent of involvement, parenchymal involvement, collateral circulation, prognosis prediction, and follow-up is magnetic resonance venography (MRV) in conjunction with magnetic resonance imaging (MRI).

REFERENCES

- 1) El Damarawy EA, El Nekiedy AM, Fathi AM et al. Role of magnetic resonance venography in evaluation of cerebral veins and sinuses occlusion. Alexandria Journal of Medicine (2012) 48, 29–34.
- 2) Zimmerman RD, Ernst RJ: Neuroimaging of cerebrovenous thrombosis, Neuroimaging clin N Amer, 1992, 2:463-485.
- 3) Nagaraja D, Tally AB. Stroke in the young in progress in Clinical Neurosciences EDT publ Sinha KK, Ranchi 1988; 2:129-45.
- 4) Khealani BA, Wasay M, Saadah M et al. Cerebral venous thrombosis: a descriptive multicenter study of patients in Pakistan and Middle East. Stroke 2008;39:2707–11.
- 5) Poon CS, Chang JK, Swarnkar Amar et al. Radiologic Diagnosis of Cerebral Venous Thrombosis: Pictorial Review .AJR 2007;189:S64–S75
- 6) Khandelwal N, Agarwal A, Kocchar R et al. Comparison of CT Venography with MR Venography in Cerebral Sinovenous Thrombosis. AJR 2006; 187:1637–1643
- 7) Ameri A, Bousser MG. Cerebral venous thrombosis. Neurol Clin 1992; 10:87–111
- 8) Bousser MG. Cerebral venous thrombosis: diagnosis and management. J Neurol 2000; 247:252–8.
- 9) Vogl TJ, Bergman C, Villringer A et al. Dural sinus thrombosis: value of venous MR angiography for diagnosis and follow up. AJR 1994; 162:1191– 1198

References

- 10) Leach JL, Fortuna RB, Jones BV. Imaging of Cerebral Venous Thrombosis: Current Techniques, Spectrum of Findings, and Diagnostic Pitfalls. *RadioGraphics* 2006; 26:S19–S43
- 11) Seon-Kyu Lee, Karel G. Brugge, Cerebral venous thrombosis in adults: the role of imaging evaluation and management. *Neuroimaging Clin N Am* 2003; 13; 139– 152
- 12) Aberombei J. Superior sagittal thrombosis in puerperium . In *Pathological and Practical Researches of the Brain and Spinal Cord* Publ. John Carfare and Sons Edinburgh 1828;
- 13) Ribes MF. Des recherches faites sur la phlebite *Revue Medical Francais ET Etrangere er Journal de clinique Del ‘Hotel Dieu et de la Charite de Paris* 1825; 3: 5.
- 14) Kalbag RM, Wolf AL. Etiology of cerebral venous thrombosis in *Cerebral Venous Thrombosis* publ. Ed Kalbagh RM, Wolf AL. Oxford University Press London 1967; pp238.
- 15) Bianchi D, Maeder P, Bogousslavesky J, et al. Diagnosis of cerebral venous thrombosis with routine magnetic resonance, an update. *Eur Neurol* 1998; 40 (4): 79-90.
- 16) Wasay M, Azeemuddin M. Neuroimaging of cerebral venous thrombosis. *J Neuroimaging* 2005;15:118-28.
- 17) Dormont D, Anxionnat R, Evrard S, Louaille C, Chiras J, Marsault C. MRI in cerebral venous thrombosis. *J Neuroradiol* 1994;21(2):81–99.
- 18) Stam J. Thrombosis of cerebral veins and sinuses. *N Engl J Med* 2005;352:1791-8.

References

- 19) Lafitte F, Boukobza M, Guichard JP, Hoeffel C, Reizine D, Illet O, et al. MRI and MRA or the diagnosis and follow up of cerebral venous thrombosis. *Clin Radiol* 1997;52:672-79.
- 20) James N. Scott, Richard I. Farb, Imaging and anatomy of the normal intracranial venous system, *Neuroimag Clin N Am* 2003; 13:1– 12
- 21) Okudera T, Huang YP, Ohta T, et al. Development of posterior fossa dural sinuses, emissary veins, and jugular bulb: morphological and radiologic study. *AJNR Am J Neuroradiol* 1994;15:1871–1883
- 22) R. H. Ayanzen, C. R. Bird, P. J. Keller, F. J. McCully, M. R. Theobald, and J. E. Heiserman. Cerebral MR Venography: Normal Anatomy and Potential Diagnostic Pitfalls. *AJNR Am J Neuroradiol* 21:74–78, January 2000
- 23) Dora F, Zileli T. Common variations of the lateral and occipital sinuses at the confluens sinuum. *Neuroradiology* 1980;20: 23–27
- 24) J. Kimber, Cerebral venous thrombosis. *Q J Med* 2002; 95:137-142.
- 25) Bousser M-G, Ross Russell RW. *Cerebral Venous Thrombosis*. London: WB Saunders, 1997
- 26) Holger Allroggen and Richard J Abbott, Cerebral venous sinus thrombosis, *Postgrad. Med. J.* 2000; 76:12-15.
- 27) Rodallec MH, Krainik A, Feydy A et al. Cerebral Venous Thrombosis and Multidetector CT Angiography: Tips and Tricks1. *RadioGraphics* 2006; 26:S5–S18

References

- 28) Herrmann KA, Sporer B, Yousry TA. Thrombosis of the internal cerebral vein associated with transient unilateral thalamic edema: a case report and review of the literature. *AJNR Am J Neuroradiol* 2004;25(8):1351–1355.
- 29) Ferro JM, Canhao P, Stam J, Bousser MG, Barinagarrementeria F; ISCVT Investigators. Prognosis of cerebral vein and dural sinus thrombosis: results of the International Study on Cerebral Vein and Dural Sinus Thrombosis (ISCVT). *Stroke* 2004;35(3):664–670.
- 30) Virapongse C, Cazenave C, Quisling R, Sarwar M, Hunter S. The empty delta sign: frequency and significance in 76 cases of dural sinus thrombosis. *Radiology* 1987;162(3):779–785.
- 31) Cure JK, Van Tassel P. Congenital and acquired abnormalities of the dural venous sinuses. *Semin Ultrasound CT MR* 1994;15(6):520–539.
- 32) Oppenheim C, Domigo V, Gouvrit JY, et al. Subarachnoid hemorrhage as the initial presentation of dural sinus thrombosis. *AJNR Am J Neuroradiol* 2005;26(3):614–617.
- 33) Chang R, Friedman DP. Isolated cortical venous thrombosis presenting as subarachnoid hemorrhage: a report of three cases. *AJNR Am J Neuroradiol* 2004;25(10):1676–1679.
- 34) Sztajzel R, Coeytaux A, Dehdashti AR, Delavelle J, Sinnreich M. Subarachnoid hemorrhage: a rare presentation of cerebral venous thrombosis. *Headache* 2001;41(9):889–892.
- 35) Pillai LV, Ambike DP, Nirhale S, Husainy SMK, Pataskar S, et al. Cerebral venous thrombosis: An experience with anticoagulation with low molecular weight heparin. *Indian J Crit Care Med* 2005; 9:14-18.

References

- 36) Osborn AG, Anne G. Osborn's Brain: Imaging, Pathology, and Anatomy, 1st Edition , Amirsys Publishing Inc,2013, pg- 225
- 37) Ferro JM, Lopes MG, Rosas MJ, Femo MA, Fontes J: Long-Term Prognosis of Cerebral Vein and Dural Sinus Thrombosis. Results of the venoport study. *Cerebrovasc Dis* 2002; 13:272-8.
- 38) Srinivasan K. Cerebral venous and arterial thrombosis in pregnancy and puerperium: a study of 135 patients. *Angiology* 1983;34:731–746.
- 39) Mas JL, Lamy C. Stroke in pregnancy and the puerperium. *J Neurol* 1998;245(6-7):305–313
- 40) Bousser MG, Chiras J, Bories J, Castaigne P. Cerebral venous thrombosis a review of 38 cases. *Stroke* 1985; 16:199-213.
- 41) Villringer A, Mehraen S, Einhüpl KM. Pathophysiological aspects of cerebral sinus venous thrombosis. *J Neuroradiol* 1994; 21:72–80.
- 42) Crawford SC, Digre KB, Palmer CA. Thrombosis of the deep venous drainage of the brain in adults. Analysis of 7 cases with review of the literature. *Arch Neurol* 1995; 52:1101–8.
- 43) Eng LJ, Longstreth WT Jr, Shaw CM, Eskridge JM, Bahls FH. Cerebellar venous infarction: a case report with clinicopathologic correlation. *Neurology* 1990;40:837-8
- 44) Anne G.Osborn, Venous Occlusions. In: *Diagnostic Neuroradiology: Stroke*. U.S.A: Harcourt Brace and Company Asia PTE LTD, Mosby – Year Book; 2004:385-395.

References

- 45) Spies JB, Berlin L. Complications of femoral artery puncture. *AJR Am J Roentgenol* 1998;170(1): 9–11.
- 46) Heiserman JE, Dean BL, Hodak JA, et al. Neurologic complications of cerebral angiography. *AJNR Am J Neuroradiol* 1994;15(8):1401–1407; discussion 1408–1411
- 47) Wetzel SG, Kirsch E, Stock KW, Kolbe M, Kaim A, Radue EW. Cerebral veins: comparative study of CT venography with intraarterial digital subtraction angiography. *AJNR Am J Neuroradiol* 1999;20(2):249–255.
- 48) Alberico RA, Barnes P, Robertson RL, Burrows PE. Helical CT angiography: dynamic cerebrovascular imaging in children. *AJNR Am J Neuroradiol* 1999;20(2):328–334.
- 49) Casey SO, Alberico RA, Patel M, et al. Cerebral CT venography. *Radiology* 1996;198(1):163–170.
- 50) Ozsvath RR, Casey SO, Lustrin ES, Alberico RA, Hassankhani A, Patel M. Cerebral venography: comparison of CT and MR projection venography. *AJR Am J Roentgenol* 1997;169(6):1699–1707.
- 51) Provenzale JM, Kranz PG. Dural Sinus Thrombosis: Sources of Error in Image Interpretation *AJR* 2011; 196:23–31
- 52) Leach JL. Anatomic variations of the dural venous sinus confluence: appearance on CT with MRI, MRV, and angiographic correlation. Presented at the 34th annual meeting of the American Society of Neuroradiology, Seattle, Washington, June 23–27, 1996.

References

- 53) Bezinque SL, Slovis TL, Touchette AS, et al. Characterization of superior sagittal sinus blood flow velocity using color flow Doppler in neonates and infants. *Pediatr Radiol* 1995; 25: 175–9.
- 54) Govaert P, Voet D, Achten E, et al. Noninvasive diagnosis of superior sagittal sinus thrombosis in a neonate. *Am J Perinatol* 1992; 9: 201– 4.
- 55) Donald W. McRobbie, Elizabeth A. Moore, Martin J. Graves and Martin R. Prince. *MRI From Picture to Proton*, Second edition , Cambridge University Press 2006, pg 32- 33.
- 56) De Coene B, Hajnal JV, Gatehouse P, et al. MR of the brain using fluid- attenuated inversion recovery (FLAIR) pulse sequences. *AJNR Am J Neuroradiol* 1992;13:1555–1564.
- 57) Bitar R , Leung G, Perng R et al, *MR Pulse Sequences: What Every Radiologist Wants to Know but Is Afraid to Ask* , RadioGraphics 2006; 26:513–537
- 58) Frahm J, Haase A, Matthaei D. Rapid three dimensional MR imaging using the FLASH technique. *J Comput Assist Tomogr* 1986;10:363– 368.
- 59) Stejskal EO, Tanner JE. Spin diffusion measurements: spin-echoes in the presence of a time-dependent field gradient. *J Chem Phys* 1965;42: 288–29
- 60) Carpenter JP, Holland GA, Baum RA, et al. Magnetic resonance venography for detection of deep venous thrombosis: comparison with contrast venography and duplex Doppler ultrasonography. *J Vasc Surg.* 1993;18:734- 741.

References

- 61) Evans AJ, Sostman HD, Knelson MH, et al. Detection of deep venous thrombosis: prospective comparison of MR imaging with contrast venography. *AJR*. 1993;161:131-139.
- 62) . Vogt FM, Herborn CU, Goyen M. MR venography. *Magn Reson Imaging Clin N Am*. 2005; 13:113-129.
- 63) David Saloner, The AAPM/ RSNA Physics Tutorials For Residents, An /introduction To MR Angiography, *Radiographics* 1995, 15:453-465
- 64) Liauw L, van Buchem MA, Spilt A, et al. MR angiography of the intracranial venous system. *Radiology* 2000; 214:678–682
- 65) Farb RI, Scott JN, Willinsky RA, Montanera WJ, Wright GA, terBrugge KG. Intracranial venous system: gadolinium-enhanced three-dimensional MR venography with auto-triggered elliptic centric- ordered sequence—initial experience. *Radiology* 2003;226(1):203–209.
- 66) Butty S, Klaus D, Hagspiel, Leung DA et al. Body MR Venography, *Radiol Clin N Am*, 2003; 40:899-919
- 67) Macchi PJ, Grossman RI, Gomori JM, Goldberg HI, Zimmerman RA, Bilaniuk LT. High field MR imaging of cerebral venous thrombosis. *J Comput Assist Tomogr* 1986;10(1):10–15.
- 68) Hinman JM, Provenzale JM. Hypointense thrombus on T2-weighted MR imaging: a potential pitfall in the diagnosis of dural sinus thrombosis. *Eur J Radiol* 2002;41:147–152.
- 69) Favrole P, Guichard J, Crassard I, Bousser MG, Chabriat H. Diffusion- weighted imaging of intravascular clots in cerebral venous thrombosis. *Stroke* 2004;35:99–103.

References

- 70) Bergui M, Bradac G. Clinical picture of patients with cerebral venous thrombosis and patterns of dural sinus involvement. *Cerebrovasc Dis* 2003; 16:211–216.
- 71) Isensee C, Reul J, Thron D. Magnetic resonance imaging of thrombosed dural sinuses. *Stroke* 1994;25:29–34.
- 72) Dormont D, Sag K, Biondi A, Wechsler B, Marsault C. Gadolinium-enhanced MR of chronic dural sinus thrombosis. *AJNR Am J Neuroradiol* 1995;16:1347–1352.
- 73) Selim M, Fink J, Linfante I, Kumar S, Schlaug G, Caplan LR. Diagnosis of cerebral venous thrombosis with echo-planar T2*-weighted magnetic resonance imaging. *Arch Neurol* 2002;59:1021–1026.
- 74) Tsai FY, Wang AM, Matovich VB, et al. MR staging of acute dural sinus thrombosis: correlation with venous pressure measurements and implications for treatment and prognosis. *AJNR Am J Neuroradiol* 1995;16:1021–1029.
- 75) Yuh WT, Simonson TM, Wang AM, et al. Venous sinus occlusive disease: MR findings. *AJNR Am J Neuroradiol* 1994;15:309–316.
- 76) Yoshikawa T, Abe O, Tsuchiya K, et al. Diffusion weighted magnetic resonance imaging of dural sinus thrombosis. *Neuroradiology* 2002;44:481–488.
- 77) Lovblad KO, Bassetti C, Schneider J, Ozdoba C, Remonda L, Schroth G. Diffusion-weighted MRI suggests the coexistence of cytotoxic and vasogenic oedema in a case of deep cerebral venous thrombosis. *Neuroradiology* 2000;42:728–731.

References

- 78) Rollins N, Ison C, Booth T, Chia J. MR venography in the pediatric patient. *AJNR* 2005; 26:50–55
- 79) Forbes KP, Pipe JG, Heiserman JE. Evidence for cytotoxic edema in the pathogenesis of cerebral venous infarction. *AJNR Am J Neuroradiol* 2001;22:450–455
- 80) Bergui M, Bradac G, Daniele D. Brain lesions due to cerebral venous thrombosis do not correlate with sinus involvement. *Neuroradiology* 1999;41: 419–424.
- 81) Schaefer PW, Grant PE, Gonzalez RG. Diffusion-weighted MR imaging of the brain. *Radiology* 2000;217:331–345
- 82) Mark E. Mullins, P. Ellen Grant, Bing Wang, R. Gilberto Gonzalez, and Pamela W. Schaefer .Parenchymal Abnormalities Associated with Cerebral Venous Sinus Thrombosis: Assessment with Diffusion-Weighted MR Imaging. *AJNR*: 25, November/December 2004
- 83) Keiper MD, Ng SE, Atlas SW, Grossman RI. Subcortical hemorrhage: marker for radiographically occult cerebral vein thrombosis on CT. *J Comput Assist Tomogr* 1995;19(4):527–531.
- 84) Doege CA, Tavakolian R, Kerskens C, et al. Perfusion and diffusion magnetic resonance imaging in human cerebral venous thrombosis. *J Neurol* 2001;248(7):564–571.
- 85) Keller E, Flacke S, Urbach H, Schild HH. Diffusion- and perfusion-weighted magnetic resonance imaging in deep cerebral venous thrombosis. *Stroke* 1999;30(5):1144–1146.

References

- 86) Hsu LC, Lirng JF, Fuh JL, Wang SJ, Shyu HY, Liu HC. Proton magnetic resonance spectroscopy in deep cerebral venous thrombosis. *Clin Neurol Neurosurg* 1998;100(1):27–30.
- 87) Nicoli F, Lefur Y, Denis B, Ranjeva JP, Confort- Gouny S, Cozzone PJ. Metabolic counterpart of decreased apparent diffusion coefficient during hyperacute ischemic stroke: a brain proton magnetic resonance spectroscopic imaging study. *Stroke* 2003;34(7):e82–e87. <http://stroke.ahajournals.org/cgi/content/full/34/7/e82>. Published June 19, 2003. Accessed July 8, 2003.
- 88) Derdeyn CP, Powers WJ. Isolated cortical venous thrombosis and ulcerative colitis. *AJNR Am J Neuroradiol* 1998;19(3):488–490.
- 89) Leach JL, Bulas RV, Ernst RJ, Cornelius RS. MR imaging of isolated cortical vein thrombosis: the hyperintense vein sign. *J Neurovasc Dis* 1996;1(3):1–7.
- 90) Ahn TB, Roh JK. Case of cortical vein thrombosis with the cord sign. *Arch Neurol* 2003;60(9):1314– 1316.
- 91) M. Boukobza, I. Crassard, M.G. Bousser, H. Chabriat . MR Imaging Features of Isolated Cortical Vein Thrombosis: Diagnosis and Follow-Up *AJNR* 30 , Feb 2009
- 92) Tang PH, Chai J, Chan YH, Chng SM, Lim CC. Superior sagittal sinus thrombosis: subtle signs on neuroimaging. *Ann Acad Med Singapore* 2008; 37:397–401
- 93) Idbaih A, Boukobza M, Crassard I, Porcher R, Bousser MG, Chabriat H. MRI of clot in cerebral venous thrombosis: high diagnostic value of susceptibility- weighted images. *Stroke* 2006; 37:991–995

References

- 94) Saposnik G, Barinagarrementeria F, Brown RD Jr., Bushnell CD, Cucchiara B, Cushman M, deVeber G, Ferro JM, Tsai FY. Diagnosis and management of cerebral venous thrombosis: a statement for healthcare professionals from the American Heart Association/American Stroke Association. *Stroke*. 2011;42:1158–1192.
- 95) Bousser MG, Ferro JM. Cerebral venous thrombosis: an update. *Lancet Neurol*. 2007;6:162–170.
- 96) Liang L, Korogi Y, Sukahara T, Onomichi M, Shigematsu Y, Yang D, et al. Evaluation of the intracranial dural sinuses with a 3D contrast enhanced MP- RAGE sequence: Prospective comparison with 2D-TOF MR venography and digital subtraction angiography. *Am J Neuroradiol*, 2001;22:481- 92.
- 97) Zilkha A, Stenzler SA, Lin JH. Computed tomography of normal and abnormal superior sagittal sinus. *Clin Radiol* 1982; 33:415-25.
- 98) De Bruijn SF, Stam J, for the CVST Study Group. Randomised, placebo- controlled trial of anticoagulant treatment with low molecular weight heparin for cerebral sinus thrombosis. *Stroke* 1999; 30:484–8.
- 99) Shroff M, deVeber G. Sinovenous thrombosis in children. *Neuroimaging Clin North Am* 2003; 13:115–138
- 100) Bousser MG. Cerebral venous thrombosis: nothing, heparin, or local thrombolysis. *Stroke* 1999; 30:481–3.

References

- 101) Einhaupl KM, Villringer A, Meister W, et al. Heparin treatment in sinus venous thrombosis. *Lancet* 1991; 338:597–600.
- 102) Barnwell SL, Higashida RT, Halbach VV, et al. Direct endovascular thrombolytic therapy for dural sinus thrombosis. *Neurosurgery* 1991; 28:135–42.
- 103) Higashida RT, Helmer E, Halbach VV, et al. Direct thrombolytic therapy for superior sagittal sinus thrombosis. *AJNR Am J Neuroradiol* 1989; 10(Suppl 5): S4–6.
- 104) Horowitz M, Purdy P, Unwin H, et al. Treatment of dural sinus thrombosis using selective catheterization and urokinase. *Ann Neurol* 1995; 38:58–67.
- 105) Frey JL, Muro GJ, McDougall CG, Dean BL, Jahnke HK. Cerebral venous thrombosis: combined intrathrombus rtPA and intravenous heparin. *Stroke* 1999;30:489–494
- 106) Benamer HT, Bone I. Cerebral venous thrombosis: anticoagulants or thrombolytic therapy. *J Neurol Neurosurg Psychiatry* 2000; 69:427–30.
- 107) Vilela P, Willinsky R, Terbrugge K. Treatment of intracranial venous occlusive disease with sigmoid sinus angioplasty and stent placement in a case of infantile multifocal dural arteriovenous shunts. *Intervent Neuroradiol* 2001; 7:51–60.
- 108) Nagaraj D, Haridas T, Taly AB, Veerendrakumar M, Subbukrishna DK. Puerperal cerebral venous thrombosis: therapeutic benefit of low dose heparin. *Neurol India* 1999;47:43–6.
- 109) Bousser MG, Barnett HJM. Cerebral venous thrombosis. In: Barnett HJM, Mohr JP, Stein BM, Yatsu FM, editors. *Stroke pathophysiology diagnosis and management*. 2nd ed. New York, NY: Churchill Livingstone Inc.; 1992.

References

110) Jeffrey J, Lisa M, Raiseer DM, et al. Cerebral sinus thrombosis diagnosed by MRI and MRV venography in cancer patients. *Neurology* 2000;55:309.

111) De Bruijin S, de haan R, Stam J. Clinical features and prognostic of cerebral venous thrombosis in a prospective series of 59 patients. *J Neurol Neurosurg Psychiat* 2001; 70:105-8.

112) Simonds GR, Truwit CL. Anatomy of the cerebral vasculature. *Neuroimaging Clin N Am* 1994;4:691–706.

113) J.L. Leach , W.M. Strub, M.F. Gaskill-Shipley. Cerebral Venous Thrombus Signal Intensity and Susceptibility Effects on Gradient Recalled-Echo MR Imaging . *AJNR* 28 , May 200

APPENDIX-VI

CONSENT FORM

ROLE OF MAGNETIC RESONANCE VENOGRAPHY IN EVALUATION OF CEREBRAL VEINS AND SINUSES OCCLUSION

GUIDE : **DR. RAVI KUMAR**

P.G. STUDENT : **DR. NIHAR .DOGGALLI**

PURPOSE OF RESEARCH:

I have been informed that the purpose of this study is Evaluation Of role of magnetic resonance venography in cerebral veins and sinuses occlusion.

PROCEDURE:

I understand that I will undergo history, clinical examination, MRI and MRV scanning.

RISKS AND DISCOMFORTS:

I understand that there is no risk involved in the above study.

BENEFITS:

I understand that my participation in this study will help to assess the Evaluation Of role of magnetic resonance venography in cerebral veins and sinuses occlusion.

CONFIDENTIALITY:

I understand that the medical information produced by the study will become a part of hospital record and will be subjected to confidentiality and privacy regulations of hospital. If the data is used for publications the identity of the patient will not be revealed.

REQUEST FOR MORE INFORMATION:

I understand that I may ask for more information about the study at any time.

REFUSAL OR WITHDRAWL OF PARTICIPATION:

I understand that my participation is voluntary and I may refuse to participate or withdraw from study at any time

INJURY STATEMENT:

I understand in the unlikely event of injury to me during the study I will get medical treatment but no further compensations. I will not hold the hospital and its staff responsible for any untoward incidence during the course of study.

Date:

Dr. **Ravi Kumar** (Guide) Dr. Nihar. Doggalli (Investigator)

STUDY SUBJECT CONSENT STATEMENT:

I/my ward confirm that Dr. NIHAR DOGGALLI has explained to me the purpose of this research, the study procedure that I will undergo and the possible discomforts and benefits that I may experience, in my own language.

I/my ward have been explained all the above in detail in my own language and I understand the same. Therefore I agree to give my consent to participate as a subject in this project.

(Participant)

Date:

(Witness to above signature)

Date:

ಒಪ್ಪಿಗೆ ಪತ್ರ

ROLE OF MAGNETIC RESONANCE VENOGRAPHY IN EVALUATION OF CEREBRAL VEINS AND SINUSES OCCLUSION

ಮಾರ್ಗದರ್ಶಿ : ಡಾ ರವಿ .ಕುಮಾರ್

ಸ್ನಾತಕೋತ್ತರ ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿ: ಡಾ ನಿಹಾರ್ ದೊಗ್ಗಳ್ಳಿ

ಸಂಶೋಧನೆಯ ಉದ್ದೇಶ:

ಸೆರೆಬ್ರಲ್ ವೇನ್ಸ್ ಮತ್ತು ಸೈನಸ್‌ಗಳ ಮುಚ್ಚುವಿಕೆಯ ಮೌಲ್ಯಮಾಪನದಲ್ಲಿ ಮ್ಯಾಗ್ನೆಟಿಕ್ ರೆಸೋನೆನ್ಸ್ ವೆನೋಗ್ರಫಿಯ ಪಾತ್ರ ಈ ಅಧ್ಯಯನದ ಉದ್ದೇಶವಾಗಿದೆ ಎಂದು ನನಗೆ ತಿಳಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ.

ವಿಧಾನ:

ಈ ಅಧ್ಯಯನದ ಉದ್ದೇಶಕ್ಕಾಗಿ ವಿವರವಾದ ಇತಿಹಾಸವನ್ನು ಒದಗಿಸಲು ಮತ್ತು ಕ್ಲಿನಿಕಲ್, ಮ್ಯಾಗ್ನೆಟಿಕ್ ರೆಸೋನೆನ್ಸ್ ಮತ್ತು ಮ್ಯಾಗ್ನೆಟಿಕ್ ವೆನೋಗ್ರಫಿಯ ಪರಿಚ್ಛೇದಗಳಿಗಾಗಿ ಒಳಗಾಗಲು ನನ್ನನ್ನು ಕೇಳಲಾಗುತ್ತದೆ ಎಂದು ನಾನು ಅರ್ಥಮಾಡಿಕೊಂಡಿದ್ದೇನೆ.

ಅಪಾಯಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಅನಾನುಕೂಲಗಳು:

ಮೇಲಿನ ಅಧ್ಯಯನದಲ್ಲಿ ಯಾವುದೇ ಅಪಾಯವನ್ನು ಒಳಗೊಂಡಿಲ್ಲ ಎಂದು ನಾನು ಅರ್ಥಮಾಡಿಕೊಂಡಿದ್ದೇನೆ.

ಪ್ರಯೋಜನಗಳು:

ಈ ಅಧ್ಯಯನದಲ್ಲಿ ನನ್ನ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆಯು ಡ್ಯೂರಲ್ ಸೈನಸ್ ಥ್ರಂಬೋಸಿಸ್ ಅನ್ನು ಪತ್ತೆಹಚ್ಚಲು ಮತ್ತು ಮೇಲ್ವಿಚಾರಣೆ ಮಾಡಲು MR ಆಂಜಿಯೋಗ್ರಫಿ ಆದ್ಯತೆಯ ವಿಧಾನವಾಗಿದೆ ಎಂದು ನಾನು ಅರ್ಥಮಾಡಿಕೊಂಡಿದ್ದೇನೆ.

ಗೌಪ್ಯತೆ:

ನನ್ನ ಗುರುತನ್ನು ಯಾವುದೇ ಮೂರನೇ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿ ಅಥವಾ ಪ್ರಕಟಣೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಬಹಿರಂಗಪಡಿಸಲಾಗುವುದಿಲ್ಲ ಮತ್ತು ವೈದ್ಯಕೀಯ ಮಾಹಿತಿಯು ಆಸ್ಪತ್ರೆಯ ದಾಖಲೆಗಳ ಭಾಗವಾಗಿರುತ್ತದೆ ಎಂದು ನಾನು ಅರ್ಥಮಾಡಿಕೊಂಡಿದ್ದೇನೆ.

ಹೆಚ್ಚಿನ ಮಾಹಿತಿಗಾಗಿ ವಿನಂತಿ:

ನಾನು ಯಾವುದೇ ಸಮಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಅಧ್ಯಯನದ ಕುರಿತು ಹೆಚ್ಚಿನ ಮಾಹಿತಿಯನ್ನು ಕೇಳಬಹುದು ಎಂದು ನಾನು ಅರ್ಥಮಾಡಿಕೊಂಡಿದ್ದೇನೆ.

ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆಯ ನಿರಾಕರಣೆ ಅಥವಾ ಹಿಂತೆಗೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳುವಿಕೆ:

ನಾನು ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆಗೆ ಒಪ್ಪಿಗೆಯನ್ನು ನೀಡಿದ್ದೇನೆ ಮತ್ತು ನಾನು ಯಾವುದೇ ಸಮಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸಲು ನಿರಾಕರಿಸಬಹುದು ಎಂದು ನಾನು ಅರ್ಥಮಾಡಿಕೊಂಡಿದ್ದೇನೆ

ಗಾಯದ ಹೇಳಿಕೆ:

ಅಧ್ಯಯನದ ಸಮಯದಲ್ಲಿ ನನಗೆ ಗಾಯವಾದಾಗ, ನನಗೆ ವೈದ್ಯಕೀಯ ಚಿಕಿತ್ಸೆ ನೀಡಲಾಗುತ್ತದೆ ಆದರೆ ಯಾವುದೇ ಪರಿಹಾರವನ್ನು ನೀಡಲಾಗುವುದಿಲ್ಲ ಎಂದು ನಾನು ಅರ್ಥಮಾಡಿಕೊಂಡಿದ್ದೇನೆ. ಅಂತಹ ಸಂದರ್ಭಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ನಾನು ಆಸ್ಪತ್ರೆ ಮತ್ತು ಅದರ ಸಿಬ್ಬಂದಿಯನ್ನು ಹೊಣೆಗಾರರನ್ನಾಗಿ ಮಾಡುವುದಿಲ್ಲ.

ದಿನಾಂಕ:

ಡಾ. ರವಿ .ಕುಮಾರ್ (ಮಾರ್ಗದರ್ಶಿ)

ಡಾ. ನಿಹಾರ್ ದೊಗ್ಗಳ್ಳಿ (ತನಿಖಾಧಿಕಾರಿ).

ಅಧ್ಯಯನ ವಿಷಯದ ಒಪ್ಪಿಗೆ ಹೇಳಿಕೆ:

ಈ ಸಂಶೋಧನೆಯ ಉದ್ದೇಶ ಮತ್ತು ಕಾರ್ಯವಿಧಾನ ಮತ್ತು ಸಂಭವನೀಯ ಅನಾನುಕೂಲಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಪ್ರಯೋಜನಗಳ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಡಾ. ನಿಹಾರ್ ದೊಗ್ಗಳ್ಳಿ ನನ್ನ ಸ್ವಂತ ಭಾಷೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ವಿವರಿಸಿದ್ದಾರೆ ಎಂದು ನಾನು ಖಚಿತಪಡಿಸುತ್ತೇನೆ.

ಆದ್ದರಿಂದ ನಾನು ಈ ಯೋಜನೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ವಿಷಯವಾಗಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸಲು ಸಮ್ಮತಿಸುತ್ತೇನೆ.

(ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವವರು)

ದಿನಾಂಕ

(ಮೇಲಿನ ಸಹಿಗೆ ಸಾಕ್ಷಿ)

ದಿನಾಂಕ

CASE PROFORMA

1. Name:

2. Age/Sex

3. Hospital No.:

4. PRESENTING SYMPTOMS-

1. Headache
2. Neurological deficit
3. Seizures
4. Loss of consciousness
5. Altered sensorium
6. Vomiting
7. Fever
8. Giddiness
9. Blurring of vision

5. HISTORY OF PAST ILLNESS:

1. Permanent Pacemaker.
2. Head injury / craniotomy.
3. Dehydration.
4. Ear discharge
5. Malignancy

6. Blood Disorder.
7. Coagulopathies.
8. Central venous catheter
9. Similar Episode in the past.

6. PERSONAL HISTORY:

1. Pregnancy.
2. Puerperium.
3. Intake of Alcohol.
4. Smoking.
5. Oral Contraceptive intake.
6. Hormone Replacement therapy.

7. CLINICAL EXAMINATION:-

BP:

PULSE:

MRI FINDINGS:

1) PARENCHYMAL CHANGES:

Lobes affected:

Haemorrhagic infarct:

Non haemorrhagic infarct:

2) DIFFUSION WEIGHTED IMAGING

Vasogenic edema:

Cytotoxic edema:

3) SUB ARACHNOID HAEMORRHAGE:

4) VENOUS SYSTEM

Superior sagittal sinus:

Right transverse sinus:

Right sigmoid sinus:

Left transverse sinus:

Left sigmoid sinus:

Straight sinus:

Vein of Galen:

Internal cerebral veins:

Superficial cortical veins:

5) COLLATERALS:

6) Other findings:

CONCLUSION

MASTER CHART

NAME	SEX	AGE	SYMPTOMS	CAUSE	PARENCHYMAL CHAI HI	NON HI	VAS ED	CYT ED	LOBES	COLLA1 SAH	SSS	T1	FLA TOF	RIGHT T1	FLAI TOF
SHRIKANTH	M	27	HA	UNKNOWN		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO
BASAVRAJ	M	55	HA	DEHYDRATION		NORMAL	NORMAL	NO	NO	RF	NO	NO	YES	YES	YES
SAAVAN	M	22	HA	DEMYELINATING DISORDER		NORMAL	NORMAL	NO	NO	LF	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO
CHAITRA	F	23	HA	UNKNOWN		NORMAL	NORMAL	NO	NO	RP	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO
RATNAWVA	F	85	HA,GD	SEPSIS		YES	NO	NO	NO	RP	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO
DASHARAT	M	33	HA, LW	UNKNOWN		NORMAL	NORMAL	NO	NO	RT,B,LF	NO	NO	YES	YES	YES
SATAVVA	F	98	SELAS	TRAUMA		YES	NO	NO	NO	LFP	NO	YES	YES	YES	YES
BASAVAKIRAN	M	30	FEVER	SEPSIS		YES	NO	NO	NO	LPT	NO	NO	YES	YES	YES
GEETA	F	35	HA,SEI	POSTPARTUM		YES	NO	NO	NO	LP	YES	NO	YES	YES	YES
SHIVAPPA	F	97	AS, GD	TRAUMA		YES	NO	NO	NO	LF	NO	YES	YES	YES	YES
BHIMANNA	M	52	AS, SEI	ALCOHOL		NO	NO	NO	NO	LP	YES	NO	YES	YES	YES
GEETA	F	22	HA	UNKNOWN		YES	NO	NO	NO	LT	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO
RAFIQ	M	25	GD	UNKNOWN		YES	NO	NO	NO	RT	NO	NO	YES	YES	YES
MALLIKARJUN	M	70	AS, LW	ALCOHOL		YES	NO	NO	NO	LP	NO	NO	YES	YES	YES
SAVITA	F	19	GD, HA, LW, SEI	DIARRHEA		NORMAL	NORMAL	NO	NO	RF	YES	NO	YES	YES	YES
BHIMANNA	M	36	HA	ALCOHOL		NORMAL	NORMAL	NO	NO	BLF	NO	NO	YES	YES	YES
BHIMAVVA	F	65	BOV	HYPERTENSION		NO	NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO	NO	NO
KASHIRAYA	M	58	HA, LW	TRAUMA		YES	NO	NO	NO		NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
SANGAPPA	M	42	GD, BOV	TRAUMA		YES	NO	NO	NO		NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
SHIVARAJ	M	30	HA, GD	SEPSIS		YES	NO	NO	NO	RP	NO	NO	YES	YES	YES
PRAKASH	M	42	GD, LW, SS	UNKNOWN		YES	NO	YES	NO	RT	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO
SHIVANAND	M	41	GD	ALCOHOL		YES	NO	NO	NO	LT	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO
RAGHAVENDRA	M	25	LOC	UNKNOWN		YES	NO	NO	NO	LT	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO
BHIMANAGOUDA	M	18	LOC	UNKNOWN		YES	NO	NO	NO	RIGHT PPR	NO	NO	YES	YES	YES
PRAKASH	M	51	HA, SEI	DEHYDRATION		NO	NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO	NO	NO
MUTTAPPA	M	26	LOC	DEHYDRATION		YES	NO	YES	YES	LT	YES	NO	YES	YES	YES
BEERAMMA	M	28	LW, AS	UNKNOWN		NO	NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	YES	YES	YES
BHIMANNA	M	50	HA, LOC	ALCOHOL		YES	NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	YES	YES	YES
SADDAM	M	36	HA, VOM	ALCOHOL		YES	NO	NO	NO	LT	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO
AKSHAY	M	28	SELAS	UNKNOWN		NORMAL	NORMAL	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO	NO	NO
ASHOK	M	30	LOC	UNKNOWN		NORMAL	NORMAL	NO	NO		NO	NO	YES	YES	YES
HAJILAL	M	60	HA, BOV	HYPERTENSION		NO	NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	YES	YES	YES
JYOTI	F	30	HA, SEI	POSTPARTUM		YES	NO	NO	NO	LT	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO
MAHANTESH	M	48	HA	UNKNOWN		NORMAL	NORMAL	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO	NO	NO
RAGHU	M	40	SELAS	SEPSIS		NORMAL	NORMAL	NO	NO		NO	NO	YES	YES	YES
SAVITRI	F	39	HA	ORAL CONT PILS		NORMAL	NORMAL	NO	NO		NO	NO	YES	YES	YES
SEETAVVA	F	45	SELAS	ORAL CONT PILS		NORMAL	NORMAL	NO	NO		YES	NO	YES	YES	YES
SAVITRI	F	22	HA	POSTPARTUM		YES	NO	NO	NO	RF	NO	NO	YES	YES	YES
CHETHAN	M	20	SELAS	DEHYDRATION		NORMAL	NORMAL	NO	NO		NO	NO	YES	YES	YES
MAHESH	M	38	SELAS	ALCOHOL		NO	YES	YES	YES		NO	NO	YES	YES	YES
RUKMINI	F	22	LW, AS	POSTPARTUM		NO	YES	YES	YES	RP, RP, LP	YES	NO	YES	YES	YES
SUNITHA	F	29	W5	POSTPARTUM		YES	NO	YES	YES	RT, RP	NO	NO	YES	YES	YES
SHIVANNA	M	65	SELAS	ALCOHOL		YES	NO	YES	YES	LT	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO
PUTTAMMA	F	25	HA	POSTPARTUM		YES	NO	YES	YES	RF	YES	NO	YES	YES	YES
VIJAY	M	26	HA, SEI	UNKNOWN		YES	NO	YES	YES	RF, LF	NO	NO	YES	YES	YES
SHIVAMMA	F	25	HA, GD	POSTPARTUM		NO	YES	NO	YES	PONS	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO
SRIKALA	F	22	HA, SEI	POSTPARTUM		YES	NO	YES	YES	LT	NO	YES	YES	YES	YES
BAHADDOOR	M	30	SELAS	ALCOHOL		NORMAL	NORMAL	NO	NO		NO	NO	YES	YES	YES
RANJITHA	F	19	HA, SEI	DEHYDRATION		YES	NO	YES	YES	RF	NO	NO	YES	YES	YES
VEENA	F	38	HA, SELVOM	SEPSIS		YES	NO	YES	NO	RT	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO
CHETHAN	M	21	HA	ALCOHOL		NO	YES	YES	YES	RF, LF	YES	NO	YES	YES	YES
CHANDRA	M	35	HA, SEI	ALCOHOL		YES	NO	YES	YES	RF, RT	NO	NO	YES	YES	YES
RAVICHANDRA	M	38	HA, AS	MASTOIDITIS		NORMAL	NORMAL	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO	NO	NO
GAVIRAJU	M	46	HA, AS	ALCOHOL		NO	YES	NO	YES	MB	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO

Master chart

NAME	RIGHT SIGN	T1	FLAI	TOF	LEFT TRAN:	T1	FLAI	TOF	LEFT SIGN	T1	FLAI	TOF	DEEP	YEN	T1	T2*	TOF	SUPERFICIA	T1	FLAI	T2*
SHRIKANTH		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO			NO	NO	NO
BASAVRAJ		YES	YES	YES		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	YES			NO	NO	NO
SAAVAN		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO		YES	YES	YES		NO	NO	NO			NO	NO	NO
CHAITRA		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO		YES	YES	YES			NO	NO	NO
RATNAWWA		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO			NO	NO	NO
DASHARAT		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO			YES	YES	YES
SATAVVA		YES	YES	YES		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO			NO	NO	YES
BASAVAKIRAN		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO			NO	NO	NO
GEETA		NO	NO	NO		YES	YES	YES		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO			YES	YES	YES
SHIVAPPA		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO			NO	NO	YES
BHIMANNA		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO		YES	YES	YES		NO	NO	NO			NO	NO	NO
GEETA		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO			NO	NO	NO
RAFIQ		NO	NO	NO		YES	YES	YES		NO	NO	NO		NO	YES	NO			NO	NO	NO
MALLIKARJUN		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO			NO	NO	NO
SAVITA		YES	YES	YES		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO			YES	YES	YES
BHIMANNA		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO			YES	YES	YES
BHIMAVVA		YES	YES	YES		NO	NO	NO		YES	YES	YES		NO	NO	NO			NO	NO	NO
KASHIRAYA		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO		YES	YES	YES		NO	NO	NO			NO	NO	NO
SANGAPPA		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO		YES	YES	YES		NO	NO	NO			NO	NO	NO
SHIVARAJ		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO		YES	YES	YES		NO	NO	NO			NO	NO	NO
PRAKASH		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO			NO	NO	NO
SHIVANAND		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO			NO	NO	NO
RAGHAVENDRA		NO	NO	NO		YES	YES	YES		YES	YES	YES		NO	NO	NO			NO	NO	NO
BHIMANAGOUDA		NO	NO	NO		YES	YES	YES		YES	YES	YES		NO	NO	NO			NO	NO	NO
PRAKASH		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO			YES	YES	YES
MUTTAPPA		NO	NO	NO		YES	YES	YES		YES	YES	YES		NO	NO	NO			NO	NO	NO
BEERAMMA		NO	NO	NO		YES	YES	YES		YES	YES	YES		NO	NO	NO			NO	NO	NO
BHIMANNA		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO			NO	NO	NO
SADDAM		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO			NO	NO	NO
AKSHAY		NO	NO	NO		YES	YES	YES		YES	YES	YES		NO	NO	NO			NO	NO	NO
ASHOK		NO	NO	NO		YES	YES	YES		YES	YES	YES		NO	NO	NO			NO	NO	NO
HAILAL		NO	NO	NO		YES	YES	YES		YES	YES	YES		NO	NO	NO			NO	NO	NO
JYOTI		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	YES		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO			NO	NO	NO
MAHANTESH		NO	NO	NO		YES	YES	YES		YES	YES	YES		NO	NO	NO			NO	NO	NO
RAGHU		YES	YES	YES		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO			NO	NO	NO
SAVITRI		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO			NO	NO	NO
SEETAVVA		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO			NO	NO	NO
SAVITRI		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO		YES	YES	YES			NO	NO	NO
CHETHAN		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO			NO	NO	NO
MAHESH		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO			NO	NO	NO
RUKMINI		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO			NO	NO	NO
SUNITHA		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO			NO	NO	NO
SHIVANNA		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO		YES	YES	YES		NO	NO	NO			YES	YES	YES
PUTTAMMA		NO	NO	NO		YES	YES	YES		YES	YES	YES		NO	NO	NO			NO	NO	NO
VIJAY		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO			NO	NO	NO
SHIVAMMA		YES	YES	YES		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO			NO	NO	NO
SRIKALA		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	YES		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO			YES	YES	YES
BAHADDOOR		NO	NO	NO		YES	YES	YES		YES	YES	YES		NO	NO	NO			NO	NO	NO
RANJITHA		NO	NO	NO		YES	YES	YES		YES	YES	YES		NO	NO	NO			NO	NO	NO
VEENA		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO			NO	NO	NO
CHETHAN		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO			NO	NO	NO
CHANDRA		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO			NO	NO	NO
RAVICHANDRA		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	YES		YES	YES	YES		NO	NO	NO			NO	NO	NO
GAVIRAJU		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO		NO	NO	NO			NO	NO	NO

IMAGE GALLERY

Case 1: Hemorrhagic acute infarct with left transverse sinus thrombosis.

Axial FLAIR image showing a haemorrhagic infarct in the left temporal lobe loss of flow void in left transverse sinus - suggestive of thrombosis.

Axial T1W image showing hyperintensity in left transverse sinus - suggestive of thrombosis.

Axial T2* image showing a haemorrhagic infarct (blooming artefact) in the left temporal lobe (red arrow) and left transverse sinus (white arrow) - suggestive of thrombosis.

2D TOF MIP image showing absence of flow (non -visualization) in the left transverse sinus - suggestive of thrombosis.

Case 2: Venous Sinus Thrombosis involving superior sagittal sinus , right transverse sinus, torcular hereophilli, sigmoid sinus , proximal internal jugular vein, and cortical veins.

Axial FLAIR image showing loss of flow void in right transverse (white arrow) and sigmoid sinuses (red arrow) - suggestive of thrombosis.

Axial T1W image showing loss of flow void in right transverse (white arrow) and sigmoid sinuses (red arrow) - suggestive of thrombosis.

Image gallery

Cortical veins appears normal signal intensity on T1/FLAIR images whereas in T2* there is evidence of blooming noted in bilateral frontal and high parietal regions (white arrows) – suggestive of cortical venous thrombosis.

2D TOF MIP image showing absence of flow (non -visualization) involving superior sagittal sinus , right transverse sinus, torcular hereophilli, sigmoid sinus , proximal internal jugular vein, and cortical veins- suggestive of thrombosis.

Case 3: Venous Sinus Thrombosis involving internal cerebral vein, vein of Galen ,straight sinus ,inferior sagittal and left transverse sinus.

Axial T2* image showing a blooming artefact in the internal cerebral vein, vein of Galen (yellow arrow) ,straight sinus (red arrow) ,inferior sagittal and left transverse sinus (white arrow) - suggestive of thrombosis.

2D TOF MIP image showing absence of flow (non -visualization) involving internal cerebral vein, vein of Galen ,straight sinus ,inferior sagittal and left transverse sinus- suggestive of thrombosis.

Case 4: Superior sagittal sinus thrombosis.

Image gallery

Axial FLAIR image showing haemorrhagic infarct in the left parietal lobe (white arrow) with loss of flow void in superior sagittal sinus (red arrow) - suggestive of thrombosis.

Sagittal T1W image showing loss of flow void in superior sagittal sinus - suggestive of thrombosis.

2D TOF MIP image showing absence of flow (non-visualization) in the anterior 2/3rd and posterior 1/3rd of superior sagittal sinus - suggestive of thrombosis.

Case 5: Right transverse sinus hypoplastic.

2D TOF MIP image showing reduced caliber of right transverse and sigmoid sinuses - suggestive of hypoplastic.

Case 6: Venous hemorrhagic infarct with thrombosis involving right cortical veins ,vein of Trolard and right transverse sinus.

Axial FLAIR image showing hemorrhagic infarct in the right parietal lobe (white arrow).

Axial T2* image showing (blooming artefact –red arrow) hemorrhagic infarct in the right parietal lobe.

Axial FLAIR image showing loss of flow void in right transverse sinus (white arrow) - suggestive of thrombosis.

Axial T2* image showing a blooming artefact in the right transverse sinus (white arrow) - suggestive of thrombosis.

2D TOF MIP image showing absence of flow (non -visualization) in the right cortical veins , vein of trolard and right transverse sinus- suggestive of thrombosis.

ETHICAL CLEARANCE CERTIFICATE

BLDE
(DEEMED TO BE UNIVERSITY)

Declared as Deemed to be University as per UGC Act, 1956
Accredited with 'A' Grade by NAAC (Cycle-2)

The Constituent College

SHRI B. M. PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE, HOSPITAL & RESEARCH CENTRE, VIJAYAPURA

BLDE (DU)/IEC/ 759/2022-23

30/8/2022

INSTITUTIONAL ETHICAL CLEARANCE CERTIFICATE

The Ethical Committee of this University met on Friday, 26th August, 2022 at 3.30 p.m. in the Department of Pharmacology scrutinizes the Synopsis of Post Graduate Student of BLDE (DU)'s Shri B.M.Patil Medical College Hospital & Research Centre from ethical clearance point of view. After scrutiny, the following original/ corrected and revised version synopsis of the thesis/ research projects has been accorded ethical clearance.

TITLE: "Role of Magnetic Resonance Venography in Suspected Cases of Cerebral Venous Thrombosis".

NAME OF THE STUDENT/PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR: DR NIHAR DOGGALLI

NAME OF THE GUIDE: DR. ANIL JOSHI, Dept. of Radiology.

Dr. Santoshkumar Jeevangi
Chairperson
IEC, BLDE (DU),
VIJAYAPURA

Institutional Ethical Committee,
BLDE (Deemed to be University)

Following documents were placed before Ethical Committee for Scrutiny

- Copy of Synopsis/Research Projects
- Copy of inform consent form
- Any other relevant document

Dr. Akram A. Shaikwadi
Member Secretary
IEC, BLDE (DU),
VIJAYAPURA

MEMBER SECRETARY
Institutional Ethics Committee
(Deemed to be University)
Vijayapura-575103, Karnataka

Smt. Bangaramma Sajjan Campus, B. M. Patil Road (Sholapur Road), Vijayapur - 586103, Karnataka, India.

BLDE (DU): Phone: +918352-262770, Fax: +918352-262300, Website: www.bldeh.ac.in, E-mail: office@bldeh.ac.in
College: Phone: +918352-262770, Fax: +918352-262015, E-mail: bmgprc.principal@bldeh.ac.in

Similarity Report ID: oid:3618:62006706

PAPER NAME

ROLE OF MAGNETIC RESONANCE VENOGRAPHY IN EVALUATION OF CEREBRAL VEINS AND SINUSES OCCLUSION

AUTHOR

Nihar Doggalli

WORD COUNT

17366 Words

CHARACTER COUNT

97254 Characters

PAGE COUNT

98 Pages

FILE SIZE

2.1MB

SUBMISSION DATE

Jun 26, 2024 9:40 AM GMT+5:30

REPORT DATE

Jun 26, 2024 9:41 AM GMT+5:30**● 8% Overall Similarity**

The combined total of all matches, including overlapping sources, for each database.

- 6% Internet database
- 7% Publications database
- Crossref database
- Crossref Posted Content database

● Excluded from Similarity Report

- Submitted Works database
- Bibliographic material
- Quoted material
- Cited material
- Small Matches (Less than 14 words)